

Lexicological Studies in Old Literary Tibetan. Onomastics

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Introduction

“Lexicological Studies in Old Literary Tibetan. Onomastics” (LS-O) provides analytical information and etymological notes on the proper names from the Old Tibetan Dictionary (OTD; otdict.com). It complements the latter and contains only additional sources, whereas the principal sources of information are provided in the dictionary. If not otherwise stated, all passages have been checked against scans available on the IDP and Gallica. Transliteration follows (Bialek 2020b). Tibetan transliteration of western sources has been adjusted.

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⤴ **Kag-la-boñ** (#136)

Ch. Géluófèng 閣羅鳳, king of the Mywa allied with Tibet in 751. Together with councillor Mgos Khri-bzañ Yab-lag and *záñ* Stoñ-rčan overthrew Se-ču in W 756/7 (PT 1287: 345, 350; Or.8212/187: 21).

⤴ **Kam keñ** (#509)

Ch. emissary who came to Tibet in the S 703/4 (ITJ 750: 143). *Kam keñ* is a transcription of Ch. family name Gān 甘 and the title *qīng* 卿 (Petech 1988a: 281).

⤴ **Kam Khri-bzañ Bye-yday** (#523)

Tibetan official (?)¹ killed in Mdo-smad in 653/4 (PT 1288: 25–6).

⤴ **Kam-ču** (#137)

Subject (?) of king Rko-te (Or.8212/187: 88).

⤴ **Kim-sañ khon čo** (#155)

Ch. princess (daughter of prince Lǐ Shǒulǐ 李守禮 and adopted daughter of Ch. Tang emperor Zhōngzōng 中宗) married to Khri Lde-gcug-brčan arrived at Śa-cal of Ra-sa in 710/11 (ITJ 750: 177). She died in W 739/40 (ITJ 750: 282) and her funeral was organised together with the funeral of Lhas-bon in W 741/2 (ITJ 750: 287–8).

⤵ **Keñ-sí** (#138)

Ch. capital Cháng'ān 長安 of the Tang dynasty captured by councillor Stag-sgra, *záñ* Stoñ-rčan, and *záñ* Bčan-ba in W 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 54).

⤵ **Keyu-sa** (#139)

Stronghold (?) located in Khar-can and captured by councillor Skyes-bzañ Rgyal-koñ in W 761/2 (Or.8212/187: 44, 73).

⤵ **Kog** (#156)

Located in Rag-tag a Mdo-smad council site in W 755/6 (Or.8212/187: 15).

¹ Dotson called him 'minister' without, however, quoting any sources for this information (Dotson 2009b: 296).

📍 **Kog-yul (#366)**

Most probably identical with Gog-yul (Gog is spelled Kog in PT 1287: 525). Its identity with Kuòzhōu 廓州 (Beckwith 1993: 129, fn. 124) is less probable for the standard Tibetan transcription of Ch. *zhōu* was *č(h)u* and not *yul*; Kuòzhōu 廓州 is attested in OLT as Gog-ču (see (Horlemann 2012: 123); (Iwao 2021: 165)).

📍 **Kwa-ču (#725)**

Ch. prefecture and/or its capital situated in the Tang period south-east of the modern town Ānxī 安西 in the Gansu province. Under Tibetan rule, Kwa-ču (including stronghold Sin-čaṅ) comprised the territories of Śa-ču and Sug-ču.

👤 **Kwag cuṅ laṅ (#510)**

Chinese emissary who came to Brag-mar to pay homage in the winter 743/4 (ITJ 750: 295). Kwag *cuṅ laṅ* is a transcription of Ch. family name Guō 郭 and the title *zhōng-láng* 中郎 (Petech 1988a: 287).

👤 **Rko-te (#265)**

King residing in the stronghold Kwa-ču (?; Or.8212/187: 88).

📍 **Rkoṅ (#266)**

Region with a centre in Bre-snar (PT 1286: 16) and including G.yug (PT 1288: 41). The official title of the rulers was *rkoṅ (d)kar po* (Rkoṅ 2, 14, 18).

📍 **Rkyaṅ-bu-chal (#505)**

Located in Zu-spug council site in S 713/4 and S 715/6 (ITJ 750: 189, 198); identified with modern-day Mkhar-rkyaṅ village in Lower Zi-sbug (OLT Zu-spug). According to *Dbay bžed*, a debate between Buddhists and Bon-pos was held there in a pig year, most probably 759 CE. for the court of *bcan po* Khri Sroṅ-lde-brcan resided in Zu-spug in S 758/9 and S 761/2.

📍 **Ske-bye (#504)**

Located in Mal-tro residence of *bcan po* Khri Maṅ-slon Maṅ-rcaṅ in 660/1 (PT 1288: 39).²

📍 **Skyi (#302)**

Region located in the Bod land along the Skyi river. Places related: Gliṅ-riṅs-cal (council site in W 692/3), Stag-cal (council site in S 693/4), Dra-cal (council site of W 712/3), Rnams (council

² (Hazod 2009: 216) speculated that *ske* could be a variant reading of *skyi*. However, his identification is based on reading *skye* instead of *ske*. Besides, Ske-bye is explicitly said to have been in Mal-tro – a region distinct from Skyi.

site of W 711/2 and W 743/4), Pyi-cal (council site in W 756/7), Bur (council site in W 761/2 and W 762/4), Byar-liñs-cal (council site in W 704/5, W 728/9, and W 746/7), Bra-ma-thañ (council site of W 686/7 and W 691/2), Śo-ma-ra (council site in W 729/30, W 731/2, and W 744/5), and Lhas-gañ-cal (council site in W 724/5, W 727/8, W 732/3, and W 733/4).

1 Skyes-bzañ Rgyal-koñ (#300)

Councillor; died in S 757/8 (Or.8212/187: 18, 19, 25).

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📍 **Khar-can (#414)**

Colonial province comprising Leñ-ču, Ba-mgo and Keyu-śan. As convincingly argued by Uray, in OLT the term Khar-c(h)an (sometimes also written with *mkhar*) “was the name of a military district stretching from the Ruo Shui to the Huang He”, “indicated the region of Liangzhou” and “served as the name of a *khrom* ‘military district (of government)’ of the Tibetan Empire” (Uray 1991: 219). One finds it in the following linguistic contexts:

<i>khar can leñ ču</i>	Or.8212/187: 33
<i>khar can ba mgo dañ keyu śan</i>	Or.8212/187: 44, 73
<i>(m)khar can khrom</i>	PT 1089: r12, 30, 33, 35; ITJ 751: 39v1
<i>mkhar chan yan čhad du</i>	PT 1287: 382
<i>mkhar can khrom čhed po</i>	ITJ 751: 38v2–3
<i>khom (sic) mkhar can pa</i>	ITJ 751: 39r3
<i>khar can phyogs su</i>	Žol S 26
<i>kwa ču [dañ kha]r can yang čad du</i>	Or.15000/496: r4 ³

These leave no doubt that Khar-can denoted a colonial province (*khrom*), in which other towns or strongholds could be located, like Leñ-ču, Ba-mgo, and Keyu-śan.⁴ Leñ-ču was most probably the capital of the colonial province (Uray 1991: 220).

📍 **Khu (#783)**

Family name.

📍 **Khu Khri-sña Dgru-zuñ (#152)**

Accused in W 678/9 together with Spuñ-rye-ryuñ and dispossessed of his properties in 680/1 (PT 1287: 88; ITJ 750: 72, 75). Khu Khri-sña Dgru-zuñ is also mentioned in an enigmatic passage in connection with the reign of Khri Sroñ-rcan:

(1)
mañ žam sum snañ dañ / khu khri sña dgruḡ zuñ gñis // ral gyi dañ brdaḡ (89) prad čhes bgyis te // (PT 1287)

[One] said “[Mgar] Mañ-žam Sum-snañ and Khu Khri-sña Dgru-zuñ verified evidences with a sword.”⁵

³ The reconstruction follows (Uray 1991: 209).

⁴ For the interpretation of *khar can leñ ču* as ‘Leñ-ču [of] Khar-can’ compare *dru gu gu zan* (ITJ 750: 97) ‘Gu-zan of Dru-gu’.

⁵ The actual meaning of the phrase *ral gyi dañ brdaḡ prad* is difficult to assess. The translation is only tentative.

📍 **Khu-ñe-mon-gaṅs (#517)**

Place where the administration of the Xa-ža was carried out in 742/3 (ITJ 750: 291). The syllables *khu ñe* seem to have rendered the same foreign toponym as *kho ñe* in Kho-ñe-du-ru. In this case, Mon-gaṅs and Du-ru would have been places located within a greater region called Kho/Khu-ñe.⁶ Since Kho-ñe-du-ru was located north of the Four Horns (see s.v. Kho-ñe-du-ru), this might well have been a region in the vicinity of (or maybe even within) the Xa-ža territory. The name Khu-ñe-mon-gaṅs is most probably of non-Tibetan origin.

📍 **Khu Xdus-can (#151)**

📍 **Khu Xbyur-lod-bcan (#150)**

Killed in W 703/4 (ITJ 750: 144; Dx 12851v: 2).

📍 **Khu Mañ-po-rje Lha-zuñ (#154)**

Active from 702/3; proclaimed as grand councillor in W 705/6 but accused the same year and dispossessed of his properties in S 707/8 (ITJ 750: 140–1, 154, 162).

📍 **Khu-le (#153)**

Toponym (text passage damaged).

📍 **Khe-rgad Mdo-snañ (#140)**

Instigator; executed in 705/6 at Bon-mo-na-la-ce (ITJ 750: 151; PT 1287: 482).

📍 **Kho-ñe-du-ru (#518)**

Place located to the north of the Four Horns, to which *bcan-po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ went for hunting wild yaks in S 724/5. For Kho-ñe, see s.v. Khu-ñe-mon-gaṅs.

📍 **Kho-brañ-cal (#519)**

Birth place of Rgyal-gcug-ru (alias Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ) in the spring 704/5 (ITJ 750: 146).

📍 **Khyi-śa-čan (#470)**

Captured by Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab in 734/5 (ITJ 750: 270); prob. located in the Pamirs or Karakoram.

In the summer 729/30 Tibetans won a battle against Chinese at Mu-le-cu-le (ITJ 750: 253) and starting in the same year Chinese were sending emissaries to the Tibetan court every year until 737/8 when they severed diplomatic relations with Tibet (ITJ 750: 278). It seems then

⁶ This parallelism was overlooked by (Shimunek 2017: 182) who interpreted *gaṅs* as ‘glacier’ instead.

that Khyi-śa-čan, sacked by Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab in 734/5 (ITJ 750: 270), was not in Chinese hands at that point. Beckwith remarks that the 730s was the time of Tibetan expansion in the Pamirs (Beckwith 1993: 110ff.) They allied with Türgiś (OLT Dur-gyis), a coalition of Western Turkic tribes, and sent *je ba* Xdron-ma-lod as a bride to the Turkic *kha gan* in 734/5 (ITJ 750: 268–9). It is therefore thinkable that Khyi-śa-čan was a town or a stronghold of one of the polities situated in the Pamirs or Karakoram. This rough localisation is supported by the annual entry for 737/8 that states that Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab went to the Bru-ža land for a military campaign which resulted in the subjugation of the king of the Bru-ža (ITJ 750: 276–7). The entry confirms that the person responsible for sacking Khyi-śa-čan was active in the western regions.

📍 **Khra-sna (#141)**

Place located in Sreyu-gžug (?; ITJ 750: 109).

👤 **Khri-sgra Stag-chab (#149)**

Councillor; active between 755/6 and 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 14, 34, 37, 40, 48, 57, 63, 78–9).

👤 **Khri-mñes Mñen-lod (#146)**

žañ and equerry (*čhibs pon*) dismissed in W 717/8 (ITJ 750: 205).

👤 **Khri-mñes Smon-zuñ (#147)**

žañ appointed as a *bruñ pa* of the Great Rcañ in S 715/6 and offered the office of grand *khud pa* in W 723/4; died in W 740/1 (ITJ 750: 199, 230, 284).

👤 **Khri Xdus-sroñ (#738)**

Tibetan *bcan po* born in Lha-luñ of Sgregs to Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcañ and Khri-ma-lod Khri-steñ from the Xbro family (PT 1286: 64–5) in W 676/7 (ITJ 750: 67), bestowed the title *khri* in W 685/6 (ITJ 750: 92–3); died on a military campaign against the Mywa in W 704/5 (ITJ 750: 148).

👤 **Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ (#739)**

Tibetan *bcan po* born as Rgyal-gcug-ru in Kho-brañ-cal to Khri Xdus-sroñ and Bcañ-ma-thog Thog-steñ from the Mčhims family in Sp 704/5 (ITJ 750: 146); bestowed the title *khri* and enthroned as Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ in S 712/3 (ITJ 750: 185–6); died probably in 754.

👤 **Khri-bañs (#142)**

bcan mo; went as a bride for the Xa-ža lord in 689/90 (ITJ 750: 102). Most probably the same person as *bcan mo* Khri-bañs mentioned in the *Annals of the Xa-ža Principality* (ITJ 1368: 12,

24, 37), called there the mother (*yum*) of Ma-ga Tho-gon *kha gan* (Uray 1978: 543f.); (Dotson 2009b: 36, 96, fn. 191).

♦ **Khri-boms (#443)**

Castle of Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad Zu-ce (PT 1287: 94, 320–2; ITJ 1375: v4–6); identified with the historical area Khri-bom around the lake Glañ-mcho in Nam-riñ county.

Place name Khri-boms recurs in other OLT texts:

(1)

de γī γog du khyuñ po spuñ sad zu ces / (94) byas pa las // γo ma lde lod bcan dañ regs ma mjal nas // mkhar khri boms su mchīs te // khri boms (95) dkuγ gañ pub nas / bcan po sroñ brcan ston mo gsol bar byas te // glo ba riñs pa / mgar yul {z}uñ (96) gīs chor nas / rañ gī mgo bčhad de gum mo // (PT 1287)

Thereafter, upon Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad Zu-ce had served [as great councillor], [he] disagreed with Xo-ma-lde Lod-bcan. Then, having gone to the castle Khri-boms, [he] prepared an ambush at Khri-boms. Having arranged to hold a feast for *bcan po* [Khri] Sroñ-brcan, the one who had been disloyal died having cut off his own head after [he] had been noticed by Mgar [Stoñ-rcan] Yul-zuñ.

(2)

bdagī sdum pa khri bomsu // dgyes skyems / (321) ston mo gsol du jī gnañ žes gsol nas // (PT 1287)

[Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad Zu-ce requested:] “Would [you] allow [me] to offer delicacies and beverage, a feast, at Khri-boms, the residence of mine?”

(3)

yul zuñ khri boms su mchīs te / brtags na // dku gañ pub par yul zuñ gīs chor nas // (PT 1287: 322)

When [Mgar Stoñ-rcan] Yul-zuñ, having gone to Khri-boms, examined [the place], he (lit. Yul-zuñ)⁷ noticed that [one] had prepared an ambush [there].

(4)

bdag rgan poγi sdum pa khri bomsu dgyes skyems ston mo gsol bar jī gnañ (ITJ 1375: v4)
[Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad Zu-ce requested:] “Would [you] allow [me] to offer delicacies and beverage, a feast, at Khri-boms, a residence of mine, an old man?”

(5)

γuñ gi rjes la // mgar yul zuñ pho brañ sa γdri (v6) bar bkay scal te // zu ce gan du mkhar khri bomsu mchīs nas /// (ITJ 1375)

Thereafter, [the *bcan po*] ordered Mgar [Stoñ-rcan] Yul-zuñ to enquire after the [next] whereabouts of the court; [thus, Mgar Yul-zuñ] went to [Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad] Zu-ce, to the castle Khri-boms.

⁷ *yul zuñ* is repeated because the clause *dku gañ pub par* brings another agent into the discourse.

All passages relate the ambush that was prepared by Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad Zu-ce against *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan. The plans were revealed to the *bcan po* by Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ. Khri-boms was apparently the seat of Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad Zu-ce. The annual entry for 684/5 treats of a council convened by great councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu at Re-skam of Dbu-ru-śod and of a cattle disease in proximity of Khri-boms. A possibility would be that the castle Khri-boms was given to the Mgar family as a reward for revealing the plot of Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad Zu-ce and therefore the council was convened near to this seat of Mgar.

Hazod identified Khri-boms with the district Khri-bom (other names: Khri-goñ, Khri-dgoñs, Khri-goms, Khri-som) in the area around Glañ-mcho lake (29°12'12.69"N, 87°23'30.21"E) in Nam-riñ county (Hazod 2009: 206b and Map 6.1a). Considering the fact that Khyuñ-po Spuñ-sad Zu-ce presumably conquered Rcañ, Bod, and northern Žaň-žuñ ((Uray 1972b: 38ff.); (Bialek 2021d)), it is possible that his seat, Khri-boms, was located that far to the west. It is however uncertain whether Khri-boms likewise denoted the area around the castle in imperial times.

📍 ¹Khri-ma-lod (#6)

je ba sent in W 740/1 as a bride to the lord of Bru-ža (ITJ 750: 283–4).

📍 ²Khri-ma-lod (#7)

(Kapstein 2000: 217, fn. 41) *Ldeyu Jo-sras*, pp. 120–121, states that Khri Lde-gcug-bcan had an elder brother Pa-chab-cha Lha Bal-po, a younger brother Lod Ma-lod, and a son Ljañ-cha Lha-dbon, who died before his Chinese bride arrived in Tibet. The 'younger brother Lod Ma-lod' is almost certainly a badly mangled record of the name of the grandmother Khri Ma-lod, the dowager empress.

Lady from the Xbro family, the wife of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan and the mother of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ (PT 1286: 64–5); died in W 712/3 (ITJ 750: 186) and buried in W 713/4 in Phyiñ-ba (ITJ 750: 190–1).

📍 Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan (#737)

Tibetan *bcan po* born prob. in 638 to Guñ-sroñ Guñ-rcan and Khon-čo Mañ-mo-rje Khri-skar (PT 1286: 63–4); died in Čhañ-bañ-sna in W 676 (ITJ 750: 66–7); reigned from 649 to 676.

📍 Khri-mo-steñs (527)

bcan mo sent to the Dags-po land in W 688/9 (ITJ 750: 101) most probably as a bride for Khri-zuñ, the king of the Dags-po. Possibly the mother of Bcan-zuñ, the successor of Khri-zuñ (cf. also (Uebach 1997a: 61)).

📍 Khri-mo-lan (#524)

bcan mo who gave a great feast to *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in Že-šiñ in Sp 675/6 (ITJ 750: 62).

👤 **Khri Gcug-lde-brcan (#143)**

bcan po born as Mu-cu-brtan prob. in 794; reigned from 815 until his death prob. in 841 (PT 1290: 2r; Or.8212/187: 68).

👤 **Khri-bcun (#736)**

jo mo (ITJ 750: 302); mother of Lhas-bon. In later sources she was titled *γjan mo*,⁸ which form might have resulted from folk etymologisation or a scribal error of the original *jo mo*, after the latter had undergone major semantic changes that made the word inappropriate for use with royal consorts.

📍 **Khri-rce (#148)**

Located in Gliñ residence of *bcan po* Khri Ṭdus-sroñ in W 701/2 and W 702/3 (ITJ 750: 136, 140) where he built a Buddhist temple (Skar 8–9).

👤 **Khri-zuñ (#59)**

King of the Dags-po, titled *γbon*; active from ca. 675/6 to W 694/5 when he died (ITJ 750: 63, 98, 101, 105, 118); prob. the son of Mañ-po-rje and the father of Bcan-zuñ.

👤 **Khri-bzañ Stag-cab (#144)**

zañ; died in S 721/2 (ITJ 750: 149, 220).

👤 **Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan (#716)**

Tibetan *bcan po* born in Brag-mar in 742 (ITJ 750: 291–2) to Khri Lde-gcug-brcan and Mañ-mo-rje Bzi-steñ from the Sna-nam family (PT 1286: 66–7); enthroned in S 756/7 acquiring the regnal name Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan (Or.8212/187: 17); abdicated in 797 in favour of Khri Lde-sroñ-brcan and died probably in 803/4.⁹

👤 **Khri Sroñ-rcan (#740)**

Tibetan *bcan po* born prob. in an ox year to Khri Slon-bcan and Ṭbriñ-ma Thog-dgos from the Ches-poñ family (PT 1286: 61–2); died in 649 (PT 1288: 15) and buried in 651/2 in Phyiñ-ba (PT 1288: 19–2).

📍 **Mkhay-bu (#205)**

Located in Duñs council site in S 720/1 (ITJ 750: 216).

⁸ (Beckwith 2003 [1983]: 281, fn. 17); (Sørensen 1994: 351).

⁹ (Bialek 2023a: 23).

📍 **Mkhays-sregs (#206)**

Prob. involved in fights between Khri Sroñ-rčan and his younger brother Bčan-sroñ (text passage damaged; PT 1288: 9). Syllable *-sregs* recurs in two other personal names from the OTA: Lho Ṃdus-sregs and Lho Ṃbriñ-po-rgyal Sum-sregs. Since both were members of the Lho family, one can speculate that also Mkhays-sregs belonged to this family. The syllables preceding this name in PT 1288 are [-]l *ta* and there is the courtesy name Rgyal-ta attested in Rgyal-ta Khri-goñ. On these grounds, the full name of the person concerned might be reconstructed as *Lho Rgyal-ta Mkhays-sregs.

📍 **Mkho (#207)**

Located in Stod residence of *bčan po* Khri Sroñ-lde-brčan in S 759/60 (Or.8212/187: 34).

📍 **Mkhris-pha-tañ (#209)**

Council site in S 708/9 and S 710/11 (ITJ 750: 167, 175).

📍 **Mkhris-pa-rca (#208)**

Council site in S 709/10 (ITJ 750: 171).

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📍 **Ga-ču** (#89)

Ch. stronghold captured by *žaṅ* Rgyal-zigs and *žaṅ* Stoṅ-rčan in 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 52, 84); modern Línxià shì 臨夏市.

📍 **Gu-rand** (#109)

Located in *Žims* place where councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu prepared the administration of the *Žaṅ-Žuṅ* in S 675/6 (ITJ 750: 64).

👤 **Gog** (#361)

A people from the Upper Regions (*stod phyogs*) inhabiting Wakhan (OLT *gog yul*) and identified with *huò-kǎn* 護侃 and *hù-mì* 護蜜 of Chinese sources. They were lost to the Tibetans in S 747/8 (Or.8212/187: 10) but paid homage together with the Black Ban-*yǎg* and the *Śig-nig* in W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 20).

(Baxter and Sagart 2014) (Schuessler 2009: 67) (Schuessler 2007: 283) (Pulleyblank 1991: 128)

<i>huò</i> 鑊				Y. [xwaw`] L. xɦuak E. ɣwak
<i>kǎn</i> 侃				
<i>hù</i> 護	MC <i>huH</i> OCM *[G] ^w ak-s	MC <i>ɣuo</i> ^C LH <i>ɣua</i> ^C OCM gwâkh	LH <i>ɣua</i> ^C OCM *wâkh	Y. xu` L. xɦuǎ` E. ɣ ^h
<i>mì</i> 蜜				

The toponym is found inscribed on a large boulder in Wakhan, where it seems to stand in isolation; no other words are written on the stone.¹⁰ One possibility is that the boulder once indicated the border between the Tibetan-ruled Gog and another polity. Since the Gog were lost to the Tibetans by the mid-8th century, this inscription would be one of the oldest preserved monuments of Tibetan written culture.

📍 **Gog-yul** (#360) ‘Gog land’

Land of the Gog people, corresponding to Wakhan; prob. identical with Kog-yul.

📍 **Gro-pu** (#106)

Located in Dra council site of S 695/6 and S 718/9 (ITJ 750: 119, 207); maybe modern Zhuópǔcūn 卓普村 (N 29°4'25.10, E 91°15'10.23). (Hazod 2009: 215) speculated that it might be identical with the modern Gro-sar, west of Grwa-nañ.

¹⁰ (Mock 2013a).

📍 **Glag (#95)**

Region including Phu-čuñ (council site of W 674/5, W 685/6, W 694/5, Sp 701/2, S 756/7, S 762/4, S 764/5) and Ryu-bye (council site of W 678/9); valley entrance: N 29°38'51.55, E 91°21'25.43.

📍 **Gliñ (#99)**

Region including Xol-byag (residence of Khri Xdus-sroñ in S 703/4) and Khri-rce (residence of Khri Xdus-sroñ in W 701/2 and W 702/3).

The most straightforward identification would be with Gliñ in northern Sde-dge (see (Ryavec 2015: 154, Map 41)) but this far-east location presents problems if the movement profile of Tibetan *bcan pos* is taken into account – they hardly ever leave the Four Horns and move within the Four Horns only along very restricted routes. Therefore I put forward an alternative hypothesis.

The toponym Poñ-lag-rañ is otherwise unknown but three years earlier, in the summer 702/3, Khri Xdus-sroñ was residing in Poñ-khri-mu-steñs (ITJ 750: 139). These are the only toponyms beginning with the syllable *poñ* in OT sources. Their localisations remain unknown but the OTA might provide some hints; namely, the residences of the *bcan po* in the preceding years were:

701/2	W	Khri-rce of Gliñ
702/3	S	Poñ-khri-mu-steñs
	W	Khri-rce of Gliñ
703/4	S	Xol-byag of Gliñ

It occurs that Poñ-khri-mu-steñs and Poñ-lag-rañ were located if not directly in Gliñ then in its immediate vicinity. Unfortunately, the localisations of the other places are likewise unknown, but considering the fact that in the winter 703/4 Khri Xdus-sroñ went to fight against the Xjañ people (ITJ 750: 145), Gliñ might have been located outside of the Bod land, on the route from the Central Horn to the territory of the Xjañ (on the Bod land, see Bialek 2021d). One possible location would be along the river *Gliñ, whose name might be preserved in Ch. Linlasang (N 30°38'28.84", E 92°14'40.14") and Linqū (N 30°38'2.99", E 92°15'43.86"); their names marked in blue on Google Maps indicate that these are rivers or rather rivulets. (The name Línqū 林曲 recurs farther west; N 30°38'8.04", E 92° 9'21.01"). To their north-east there is also a town called Gliñ-mthil (Ch. Líndī 林堤乡; N 30°58'4.33", E 92°34'36.95"). In the western part of the valley that connects Linlasang/Linqū to the Sangqu/Miggi river and farther to Xdam-gzuñ is located the modern town of Yos-čhags (Ch. Yóuqiàxiāng 油恰乡; N 30°35'38.36", E 91°52'47.06"), whose name brings to mind the OLT Xol-byag. It seems possible that Khri Xdus-sroñ set on from Xdam-gzuñ via the Sangqu/Miggi valley in the west (N 30°33'16.65", E 91°45'42.00") and the *Gliñ valley and then either towards the plain east of Gliñ-mthil or towards Lha-ri and further to Čhab-mdo (Ch. Chāngdū 昌都) or down the Yid-yoñ river (LT *yid yoñ gcañ po*):

1. Xdam-gźuñ > Sangqu/Miggi > Linlasang/Linqu > Gliñ-mthil (along Midi Zangpo) > Čhab-mdo > Xjañ
2. Xdam-gźuñ > Sangqu/Miggi > Linlasang/Linqu > Lha-ri > Čhab-mdo (from Lha-ri to Čhab-mdo the route would be identical with the *rgya lam*, Tibet-Sichuan tea road, see (Ryavec 2015: 68–9, Map 16)) > Xjañ (along the southern trade route)
3. Xdam-gźuñ > Sangqu/Miggi > Linlasang/Linqu > Lha-ri > down the Yid-yoñ river

📍 **Gliñ-kar-chal (#97)**

Located in Rcañ council site of W 690/1 (ITJ 750: 106); identified with 15th c. Gliñ-dkar-rjoñ in Upper Xu-yug (OLT Xo-yug).

📍 **Gliñ-riñs-cal (#98)**

Located in Skyi council site in W 692/3 (ITJ 750: 112).

📍 **Gle-ma (#96)**

Located in Par a Mdo-smad council site in W 706/7 (ITJ 750: 158).

👤 **Glo-bo (#100)**

A people identified with modern Glo-bo (Mustang, Nepal) who was subjugated together with the Rcañ-rhyay by great councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcañ Yul-zuñ in 652/3 (PT 1288: 21–2).

📍 **Dgos-dbye (#72)**

Place where emissaries from Upper Regions paid homage in S 721/2 (ITJ 750: 219–220).

👤 **Mgar (#785)**

Family name.

👤 **Mgar Khri-sgra Xji-rmun (#796)**

(Dotson 2007a: 202): From the edict of Khri Sroñ-lde-bcañ preserved by Dpaḡ-bo Gcug-lag, it appears that Mgar Xji-rmun is the highest rank among ministers of the interior; fn. 203: This rank may have developed from the personal name of one of Tibet's prime ministers, Mgar Khri-sgra Xji-rmun; (Dotson 2009b: 133–4, fn. 366) From the edict of Khri Sroñ-lde-bcañ preserved by Dpaḡ-bo Gcug-lag, it appears that Mgar-yji-rmun is the highest rank among ministers of the interior. In the list of those who swore to the edict, which likely dates to circa 779, the first of the ministers of the interior (*nañ blon*) is Minister Gra-yji Žañ Rams-śags. Having initially read this as simply a peculiar name, I am inclined now to read this as 'the Gra-yji/Mgar Ji(sic)-rmun minister, Žañ [Xbro Khri-zu] Rams-śags'; (Dotson 2012: 173, fn. 28): From the edict of Khri Sroñ-lde-bcañ preserved by Dpaḡ-bo Gcug-lag, it appears that Mgar Xji-rmun is the highest rank among ministers of the interior.

On a few occasions, Dotson argued for the interpretation of *gra yji* from KhG as a title. The respective passage reads: *nañ blon la/ś/ blon gra yji žañ rams śags/* (Xphreñ-ba 1962: 109v5–6) 'Among councillors of the interior: councillor Gra-yji, žañ Rams-śags'. What follows it is a list of people whose names are preceded either by *žañ* or *blon*: *žañ qa srin/ ža śña khri gñen/ blon*

klu goñ/ yon ka lha mcho/ blon śad bcan/ blon srin skyugs/ blon ydus ston/ žaň stag cha ba/ žaň legs ydus/ (ibid.) The next list, of councillors of the exterior (*phyi blon*), also contains simple disyllabic names. The first list that contains the names of *žaňs* and great councillors (ibid., ll. 4–5) has full names that consist of courtesy names and given names, although no family names are provided.

Dpay-bo Gcug-lag certainly had access to very old documents but the text, as it has come down to us, attests to too many scribal or copy errors to be trusted blindly. I think it more probable that *blon gra yji* is a person distinct from *žaň rams śags*, despite the lacking *śad* in-between. Should this not be the case, it would still be impossible to identify *gra yji* with *mgar yji rmun* from Or.8212/187: 60 for they share only one syllable: *yji*. Apart from that, in the name *mgar yji rmun* syllable *yji* forms one phonological word with *rmun* and not with *mgar*. And finally, there are no analogous examples of titles being formed from proper names in OLT.

On the other hand, this *mgar yji rmun* strikingly resembles the name of Mgar Khri-sgra Xji-rmun. According to the OTC, Mgar Khri-sgra Xji-rmun was the first grand councillor from the Mgar family (cf. (Dotson 2009b: 150)), praised for his wisdom in PT 1287: 79–83. Therefore I think that the passage in Or.8212/187: 60 praises Mčhims Rgyal-zigs Śu-theñ by comparing his competences to those of the famous Mgar Khri-sgra Xji-rmun.

1 Mgar Khri-ybriň Bcan-brod (#202)

Prob. a son of Mgar Stoň-rcan Yul-zuň; Qīnlíng 欽陵 of Ch. sources. Councillor proclaimed as grand councillor in 685/6. Between 687/8 and 689/90 he stayed in Dru-gu-gu-zan. At Stag-la-rgya-dur he fought a battle with the Chinese general Xwaň žaň śo in 695/6; having drawn to the Great and Small Coň-ka in W 698/9, he seized Thug *pu śi*, a great general of the Chinese; fled to China after being accused in 698/9. Active years: 673/4–698/9 (PT 1287: 109; ITJ 750: 57, 75, 77, 91–2, 92, 94, 97, 103, 104, 105–6, 115, 121, 123, 127).

The family affiliation of Khri-ybriň Bcan-brod is never stated in the OTA. However, it seems legitimate to assume that councillor and later great councillor Khri-ybriň Bcan-brod of the OTA is identical with great councillor Mgar Khri-ybriň Bcan-brod of the OTC (PT 1287: 109).

1 Mgar Sta-gu Ri-zuň (#528)

Convened the winter council of 687/8 in Bzaň-sum-cal (ITJ 750: 98–9); seized by the Sog-dag in S 694/5 (ITJ 750: 117).¹¹ According to Ch. sources, he was a son of Mgar Stoň-rcan Yul-zuň; the sources call him Xīduōyú 悉多于 (Garatti 2015: 163).

1 Mgar Stoň-rcan Yul-zuň (#204)

Lù Dōngzàn 祿東贊 of Ch. sources; grand councillor who led *bcan mo* Mun-čhaň koň čo to the Bod land in 641/2, subjugated the Glo-bo and Rcaň-rhyay people in 652/3, wrote down the

¹¹ Dotson called him 'minister' (Dotson 2009b: 296) but no corresponding term is used in the text. Without providing the sources, Garatti stated that he lost Khotan (Garatti 2015: 161).

text of the sovereign laws at Xgor-ti in 655/6, conquered the Xa-žas between 659/60 and 665/6. He died at Ris-pu in 667/8 (PT 1287: 101–2; PT 1288: 11, 21, 23, 27, 29, 31, 33, 35, 36, 39, 40, 41, 43, 44, 45, 46, 48).

👤 **Mgar Xbriñ-rcan Rcañ-ston (#742)**

Together with Pa-cab Rgyal-can Thom-po prepared sheaves of Left Horn in W 690/1 (ITJ 750: 106–7). According to Chinese sources, he was a son of Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ; the sources call him Zànpó 贊婆 (Garatti 2015: 163). He fled to China in 699 and died shortly afterwards (Garatti 2015: 162).

👤 **Mgar Mañ-žam Stag-cab (#203)**

Active from 681/2 onward. In 685/6, he had a family conflict with grand councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu (ITJ 750: 79, 82, 90–1).

👤 **Mgar Bcan-ñen Guñ-rton (#200)**

Accused of disloyalty in S 695/6 and killed at Lcañ-bu of Ñen-kar in W 695/6 (ITJ 750: 119, 120, 121).

👤 **Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu (#201)**

Prob. a son of Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ; Zànxīruò 贊悉若 of Ch. sources. Councillor proclaimed as grand councillor after the death of Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ in 667/8. He had a family conflict with Mgar Mañ-žam Stag-cab in 685/6 and died at Sum-ču-bo of Śaṅs; active years: 673/4–685/6 (PT 1287: 105–7; ITJ 750: 57, 64, 67–8, 76, 77, 78, 81, 84, 86, 90, 91).

👤 **Mgos Khri-bzañ Yab-lag (#145)**

Together with žaṅ Stoñ-rcan overthrew stronghold Teyu-ču and established the colonial government of Rma anew in 755/6; together with žaṅ Stoñ-rcan and Kag-la-boñ overthrew Se-ču in W 756/7; together with žaṅ Stoñ-rcan and žaṅ Bcan-ba overthrew the Little Coñ-ka in W 759/60; installed as grand councillor in 764/5 (Or.8212/187: 13, 21, 22, 32, 35, 37, 60).

📍 **Xgor-ti (#395)**

Place where grand councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ wrote down the text of the first known Tibetan laws (PT 1288: 29); identified with the present-day Gorte (Ch. Guǒdé 果德; N 30°21'52, E 91°01'59).

👤 **Rgya 'Chinese; a person of Chinese descent' (#372)**

👤 **Rgya-sto (#257)**

žaṅ (ITJ 750: 158, 178).

📍 **Rgyal-ta Khri-goñ (#258)**

Together with coundillor Skyes-bzañ Rgyal-koñ convened the council at Pyi-cal of Skyi in W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 19).

📍 **Rgyas (#260)**

Region including Luñ-riñs (council site in 681/2).

📍 **Rgyod (#261)**

Mdo-smad council site in W 715/6, W 724/5 and W 728/9 (ITJ 750: 201, 235, 251).

📍 **Sgyog-ram (#298)**

Council site in 682/3 (ITJ 750: 81).

📍 **Sgregs (#297)**

Identified with CT Sgrags (valley entrance: N 29°19'19.11, E 91°16'49.57). Places related: Lha-luñ and Bya-cal.

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📍 Ñañ-mo-gliñ (#400)

Located in Mchar-bu-sna residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rčan in S 740/1 (ITJ 750: 283).

👤 Ñan-lam Stag-sgra Klu-khoñ (#91)

Son of Ñan-lam Zla-goñ (Žol N 38–9); councillor later appointed as grand councillor of the interior (*nañ blon čhen*; Žol E 1–5) and eulogised in the Žol inscription. Together with *žañ* Mčhims Rgyal-zigs Śu-theñ, *žañ* Stoñ-rčan, and *žañ* Bcan-ba overthrew Keñ-śi in 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 53, 86; Žol S 54–63).

📍 Ñan-lam-cal-sar-pa (#90)

Residence of Khri-ma-lod in Sp 701/2 (ITJ 750: 87). May be identical with the modern district Chal Guñ-thañ, east of Lha-sa (Hazod 2010: 33).

👤 Rñegs Khyi-ma-re (#255)

👤 Rñegs Mañ-žam Stag-cab (#256)

Proclaimed as grand councillor by *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rčan in Sp 725/6; died in S 727/8 (PT 1287: 110; ITJ 750: 213, 237–8, 239, 241, 244).

📍 Śñur-ba (#287)

Castle that belonged first to Mñan Xji-zuñ and later to Myañ Mañ-po-rje Žañ-snañ, whose subject Pa-chab Gyim-po destroyed it (PT 1287: 311–4; PT 1288: 4–5).

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1 Čaṅ yḡwan yge (#511)

Ch. emissary who paid homage in the summer 744/5 (ITJ 750: 296–7). Čaṅ yḡwan yge is a transcription of Ch. family name Zhāng 張 and the title *yuán-ài* 元礙 (Petech 1988a: 288).

1 Čaṅ ydo sí (#576)

Ch. emissary, paid homage in the summer 731/2 (ITJ 750: 259). The first syllable *čaṅ* is a transcription of Ch. family name Zhāng 張 (Petech 1988a: 283).¹²

9 Či-ybos (#53)

Located in Yol of Mdo-smad council site of W 703/4 (ITJ 750: 144).

9 Ču-bgo (#57)

Region including Rteyu-mkhar and located not far away from Sgregs (ITJ 750: 280).

1 Če-dog-pan (#357)

Prob. a people; its emissary paid homage in 697/8 (ITJ 750: 125).

1 Če Snaṅ-rcan (#45)

Official mentioned in W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 21).

1 Čog-ro Maṅ-po-rje Khyi-čuṅ (#56)

Councillor; drew to the Dru-gu land in 736/7 and carried out the administration of the Ya-ža people at Khu-ṅe-mon-gaṅs in S 742/3. In 745/6 fought together with the lord of the Ya-ža against the stronghold Jid-par (ITJ 750: 274, 291; Or.8212/187: 5, 11).

1 Čog-ro Rma-goṅ (#49)

Installed as *bruṅ pa* in the place of *žaṅ Tre-goṅ* during the council at Dra-bye in W 745/6 (ITJ 750: 301).

9 Lčags-rce (#166)

Stronghold regained by Bzo-žal-čos in W 741/2 (ITJ 750: 287).

¹² The Ch. source of *ydo sí* remains unknown.

📍 ¹Lčañ-bu (#164)

Located in Byar residence of *bcan po*'s court in W 758/9, W 761/2, W 762/3, and 764/5 (Or.8212/187: 31, 43, 47, 56, 62, 71, 77).

📍 ²Lčañ-bu (#717)

Located in Stod (or Stod-luñs in Lčañ S 15), possibly within estates of the Ches-poñ family, the *bcan po*'s court's residence in W 757/8 (Or.8212/187: 27). During the reign of Khri Gcug-Ide-brcan, *žañ* Ches-poñ Ña-sto built there a temple (a dependency of the temple of Xon-čañ-do, Lčañ S 25–6) and erected a stone pillar with an inscription (Lčañ inscription). In later times, the Karma-pa monastery Stod-luñ-mchur-phu replaced the old temple.

📍 ³Lčañ-bu (#165)

Located in Ñen-kar place where Mgar Bcan-ñen Guñ-rton was executed in W 695/6 (ITJ 750: 121); identical with modern Lčañ-bu (N 29°50'23.83, E 91°33'2.31).

📍 Lciyu-luñ (#167)

Located in Dbu-ru-śod council site in S 724/5 (ITJ 750: 233).

👤 Lčog-la (#168)

A people, prob. neighbouring the *Žañ-žuñ*, who revolted in S 674/5.

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1 Čhog-ro Khoñ-ge (#564)

Accused in S 711/2 (ITJ 750: 180).

1 Čhog-ro Khri-gzigs Gnañ-khoñ (#48)

Convened the council of Mdo-smad in Gce-nam-yor in W 711/2 (ITJ 750: 182–3).

1 Čhog-ro Sña Žin-koñ (#50)

Installed as *mñan* in S 723/4; dismissed as a councillor of Kim-šeñ koñ čo in W 730/1 (ITJ 750: 228, 257).

9 Čhos-goñ (#51)

Located in Pa-noñ council site in S 724/5 (ITJ 750: 233).

1 Mčhims Rgyal-zigs Śu-theñ (#259)

žañ; together with *žañ* Stoñ-rcan overthrew Xbu-siñ-kun, Zin-ču, and Ga-ču in 762/4; together with councillor Ñan-lam Stag-sgra Klu-khoñ, *žañ* Stoñ-rcan, and *žañ* Bcan-ba overthrew Keñ-ši in 762/4. Was bestowed a letter of turquoise in S 764/5 (Or.8212/187: 15, 25, 51, 52, 53, 55, 59, 65, 83, 85, 85–6).

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ǰ **ǰi-ma-khol** (#133)

Place where a fortified encampment was built in 668/9 and where in 670/1 many Chinese were slaughtered (ITJ 750: 49, 51); identified with Ch. Dàfēichuān 大非川 within the Xa-ža territory south of Lake Kokonor.

ǰ **ǰid-par** (#134)

Stronghold, against which the lord of the Xa-ža and councillor Mañ-pho-rje fought in 745/6 (Or.8212/187: 5).¹³

ǰ **ǰeyu ǰaṅ sí** (#512)

Ch. emissary who paid homage in S 735/6 (ITJ 750: 272). ǰeyu ǰaṅ sí is a transcription of Ch. family name Zhào 趙 and the title *cháng-shǐ* 長史 (Petech 1988a: 286).

ǰ **ǰeyu ǰaṅ só** (#513)

Ch. emissary who paid homage in S 699/700 (ITJ 750: 129). ǰeyu ǰaṅ só is a transcription of Ch. family name Zhào 趙 and the title *shàng-shū* 尚書 (Petech 1988a: 280).

ǰ **ǰor-goṅ-sna** (#135)

Located in the Xa-ža land residence of *bcan po*'s court in W 727/8 (ITJ 750: 244).

ǰ **ǰjon** (#122)

Located in Yar-γbrog residence of Khri-ma-lod in S 702/3 (ITJ 750: 139).

ǰ **ǰjaṅ** (#781)

(Desgodins 1899: 351) nom de tribu er de pays au N.-O. du Yun-nan; WtS.20: 366b: auch *ljaṅ* ein Land, Volk, chin[esisch] 姜 Chiang bzw. 羌 Ch'iang; Bez[eichnung] für Nan-chao.

(Bacot, Thomas, and Toussaint 1940: 124, fn. 8): Pays des Mo so; (Thomas 1935–55.III: 43) the Nan-chao kingdom; (Ches-brtan 1995: 71, n. 2): ǰdir (PT 1287: 334 – JB) ǰjaṅ zes bya ba ni ǰjaṅ sa dam zes paṅi yul yin žiṅ. da ltaṅi yun nan žiṅ čhen gyi ta li daṅ li čaṅ la sogs paṅi yul gru spyiṅi miṅ ṅo; (Klu-γbum-rgyal 2006: 195, n. 3): ǰdir (PT 1287: 334 – JB) ǰjaṅ zes bya ba ni ǰjaṅ sa dam zer žiṅ. ǰjaṅ ni da lta yun nan žiṅ čhen nub rgyud kyi ta li daṅ li čaṅ la sogs paṅi yul gru spyi daṅ. sa dam ni deṅi bye brag li čaṅ kho naṅi miṅ yin. lo graṅs ṅis brgya ṅa gsum gyi riṅ la khwa la kag daṅ kag la boṅ sogs rgyal bo (sic) bču gsum rim par byuṅ ba yin la. bcan po rnam kyis de dag la bcan poṅi gčuṅ zes brjod čin. thaṅ gi rgyal bos (sic) kyaṅ waṅ gi ǰjaṅ sa lan maṅ bor byin yod pa red; (Petech 1988c: 1080): the Mo so country, i.e. the region of Li-chiang on the Yangtze-kiang; c. 720 ǰjaṅ was to become the northernmost section of the new kingdom of Nan Chao; (Uebach 2003: 25): comprised the tribes of the Black and White Mywa; situated on the south east border of Tibet, in present day Yunnan. According to the Annals, it had been subjugated by *bcan*

¹³ Beckwith's identification with Shíbǎo 石堡 (Beckwith 1993: 129, fn. 124) is flawed because 石 had a velar coda.

po Khri Ṭdus-sroñ in 703 A.D. [...] By the end of the eighth century Ṭjañ allied with China, the western part of Sichuan, however, continued to be under Tibetan control; (Dotson 2009b: 102, fn. 217): Ṭjañ/Ljañ was located to the southeast of Tibet and refers to either the Moso peoples of northwest Yunnan or to Nanzhao, but Nanzhao was not yet established as a unified kingdom until the middle of the eighth century.

For an overview of the Ṭjañ in the OLT sources, see s.v. Mywa. The origin of the proper name in Tibetan could not be clarified yet. (Johnston 1908: 223 & 279ff.) observed that in his times the name was used by Tibetans for a people whose endonym was Naxi (Ch. Nàxī 納西) or Mosuo (Ch. Mósuō 摩梭). One hypothesis would see the origin of the word in Ch. Qiāng 羌 (Rock 1947: 192–3). We can also speculate whether it might have been a borrowing from Ch. jiāng 江 ‘river’, frequently restricted in its use to Yangtze – the most important river in northern Yunnan. Both these hypotheses, however, encounter serious problems when juxtaposed with the reconstructed Middle Chinese values of the words. Another possibility then would be for ṽjañ to have been borrowed from Ch. yáng 陽 ‘sunshine; sunny side; south side’ (cf. (Schuessler 2007: 558) for the Chinese Nanzhao means ‘Southern Zhao’ from the dominant group Mengshe Zhao originally located furthest to the south ((Backus 1981: 49). Finally, ṽjañ might have represented the same syllable cháng 長 that is transcribed in the Chinese name of the dynasty Dàchánghé 大長和 that replaced the Nanzhao dynasty in 902, presuming the Chinese name is only an approximation of the original name (Backus 1981: 161); (Ecsedy 1984: 179, fn. 58). Since none of the hypotheses can be deemed satisfying, I deem the problem unsolved.

♦ Ṭjañ-yul (#121) ‘Ṭjañ land’

Land of the Ṭjañ people (ITJ 750: 145).

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📍 Ña-maṅs-chal (#220)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Maṅ-slon Maṅ-rčan in W 671/2 (PT 1288: 52).

📍 Ña-śa-chal (#222)

Located in Phul-po council site of W 689/90 and residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rčan in W 715/6 (ITJ 750: 103, 199–200).

📍 Ñam-pu (#225)

Located in Rag-tag a Mdo-smad council site in W 708/9 (ITJ 750: 169).

📍 Ñas (#226)

Region of Mdo-smad including Žo-thaṅ (council site of S 761/2).

📍 Ñen-kar (#229)

Residence of *bcan pos* in 651/2–653/4, 677/8–688/9, 691/2–693/4, W 714/5, and W 759/60 (PT 1288: 19, 21, 23; ITJ 750: 70, 73, 74, 75, 78, 81, 84, 86, 90, 94, 97, 100, 108, 111, 114, 195; Or.8212/187: 36); identified with modern Lo valley (valley entrance: N 29°51'16.85, E 91°33'53.44). Places related: Thaṅ-bu-ra (residence of *bcan po* Khri Ṃdus-sroṅ in 689/90) and ³Lčaṅ-bu.

📍 Ñen-kar rñiṅ-pa (#228)

Residence of Ziṅ-po-rje Stag-skyā-bo (PT 1287: 118) identified with modern Ñen-po-mkhar (N 29°55'55.34, E 91°34'49.31).

📍 Gñi-jī-gen (#101)

Located in Mdo-smad council site in S 717/8 (ITJ 750: 203–4).

📍 Mñald (#210)

Identical with LT Gñal/Sñal (?). Places related: Gzen.

📍 Sña-mo-steṅs (#522)

bcan mo married to Sña-śur Spuṅs-rye-rgyug in W 671/2 (PT 1288: 53). One can speculate whether the first syllable of her name, *sña*, was not added from her spouse family (?) name Sña-śur. Otherwise the coincidence would be difficult to explain.

📍 **Sña-śur Spuñs-rye-rgyug (#307)**

Married to *bcan mo* Sña-mo-steñs in W 671/2 (PT 1288: 53); id. with Spuñ-rye-ryuñ?

📍 **Sñiñ-druñ (#309)**

Region identified with modern Sñiñ-groñ (Ch. Ningzhong 宁中; N 30°22'40.01, E 90°54'45.41). Places related: Sna-riñs and G.ye-thal-ba-goñ.

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⤴ Ta-čhig (#383)

A people whose emissaries paid homage in S 732/3 (ITJ 750: 262).

⤴ Ton-ya-bgo *kha gan* (#329)

Transcription of Turk. *ton yabγu xağan* which was a title held by the founder of the dynasty of Yabghus of Tukharistan (= *tōng yè hù kèhán* 統葉護可汗 of Ch. sources; (Beckwith 1993: 68n80)). According to Clauson, OTurk. *yabγu* [jabγu] was “a title of great antiquity, [...]. In the Türkü period it was, like *şad*, a title conferred by the *xağan* on close relatives and normally carried with it the duty of administering part of the *xağan*'s dominion” (Clauson 1972: 873). It was a Turkish title of nobility although its denotation was changing over time with socio-historical circumstances. It is widely attested in various languages of Central Asia (<https://iranicaonline.org/articles/jabguya>). Ton-ya-bgo *kha gan* paid homage in W 694/5 and in W 699/700 and was sent back to the Dru-gu land in S 700/1 (ITJ 750: 117, 130–1, 133).

📍 Mtoñ-sod (#516)

Region administrated by the Tibetan Empire but apparently located outside of the Four Horns. Its administration was carried out in W 730/1 from Gce-nam-yor (ITJ 750: 258). Servants of the sentenced Lañ and Xbal families were banished to Mtoñ-sod in S 755/6 (Or.8212/187: 12–3).

📍 Rteyu-dkyus (#273)

Located in Yol of Mdo-smad council site of 706/7 (ITJ 750: 159).

📍 Rteyu-mkhar (#274)

Located in Ču-bgo council site of W 682/3 and W 738/9 (ITJ 750: 82, 280).

📍 Ltam (#183)

Region including Ra-sñon (residence of Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcañ in S 671/2).

📍 Ltams (#184)

Located in Mal-tro council site in S 714/5 (ITJ 750: 193).

⤴ Sta-gu Ri-cab (#530)

Convened the council of Mdo-smad in Gce-nam-yor in 710/1 (ITJ 750: 178); as a councillor convened a council in Čhos-goñ of Pa-noñ in 724/5 (ITJ 750: 233–4).

📍 ¹Stag-cal (#319)

Located in Duñs council site in W 673/4 and residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ in S 720/1 and S 721/2 (ITJ 750: 59, 215, 219).

📍 ²Stag-cal (#320)

Located in Skyi council site in S 693/4 (ITJ 750: 114).

📍 Stag-la-rgya-dur (#321)

Battlefield between grand councillor Mgar Khri-ybriñ Bcañ-brod and the Ch. general Xwañ Žaň-śo in W 695/6 (PT 1287: 523; ITJ 750: 122).

📍 Stoň-rcañ (#323)

žaň; together with councillor Mgos Khri-bzañ Yab-lag overthrew stronghold Teyu-ču and established the colonial government of Rma anew in 755/6; together with councillor Mgos Khri-bzañ Yab-lag and Kag-la-boň overthrew Se-ču in W 756/7; together with councillor Mgos Khri-bzañ Yab-lag and *žaň* Bcañ-ba overthrew Little Coň-ka in W 759/60, and Zoň-ču and Zaňs-kar in W 761/2; together with Mčhims *žaň* Rgyal-zigs Śu-theñ overthrew Xbu-śiñ-kun, Zin-ču, Ga-ču in 762/4; together with Mčhims *žaň* Rgyal-zigs Śu-theñ, councillor Nan-lam Stag-sgra Klu-khoň, and *žaň* Bcañ-ba overthrew Keň-śi in 762/4. Proclaimed as general of all frontiers (*so mtha bzī dmag phon*) was bestowed a letter of turquoise in S 764/5 (Or.8212/187: 13, 21, 26, 30–1, 35, 37, 44, 51, 53, 61, 67, 74, 83, 86).

📍 Stod (#322)

Stod valley identical with Stod-luñs (Lčaň 15; valley entrance: N 29°39'17.78, E 90°58'1.84), including Mkho (residence of Khri Sroň-lde-brcañ in S 759/60), Moň (council site in S 757/8), and ²Lčaň-bu (court's residence in W 757/8).

📍 Stod-phyogs (#369) 'Upper Regions'

Toponym referring to the Pamir and neighbouring areas.

th

📍 **Thaṅ-bu-ra** (#328)

Located in Ńen-kar residence of *bcan po* Khri Ṭdus-sroṅ in 689/90 (ITJ 750: 102).

👤 **Thug pu sí** (#514)

According to ITJ 750: 127–8, *rgyaṅi dmag pon čhen po* ‘a great general of the Chinese’ caught in the winter 698/9 by great councillor Mgar Khri-ṅbriṅ Bcan-brod in the Great and Small Coṅ-ka. Thug *pu sí* transcribes an unknown Ch. family name¹⁴ and the title *fù-shǐ* 副使 (Petech 1988a: 280). Beckwith translated the Chinese title as ‘assistant commissioner’ (1993: 61, fn. 38) which, however, disagrees with the Tibetan description of the person as a great general. It might be that the Tibetans exaggerated in ranking Thug *pu sí*.

📍 **Theyu-ču** (#327)

Chinese stronghold conquered by Khri-bzaṅ and *žaṅ* Stoṅ-rcan in 755/6 (ITJ 750: 135, 137; Or.8212/187: 13, 15).

¹⁴ Petech speculated that it might have been Dú-gū 獨孤 (ibid.)

d

1 Dags-po (#587)

(Uray 1960a: 206–7): Diese Landschaft lag östlich von Xol-kha und Yar-luñ am nördlichen oder an den beiden Ufern des Gcañ-po und ist im wesentlichen mit dem heutigen Dwags-po identisch. [...] der Lehnstaat Dags-po fiel zwischen 714 und 718 dem Geschlechte Mčhims zum Opfer; (Uray 1988a: 1504): is known from pre-eleventh century literature and documents in the forms of Dags, Dags-yul, Dags-śul and mainly of Dags-po; in the 16th–18th centuries supplanted by the spelling Dwags-po.

Two arguments speak for *dags po* as referring to a group of people: 1. the OTA knows the term *dags yul* as a designation of the region (ITJ 750: 101); and 2. red tallies (*khram dmar po*) were issued for populations (the only exception was the red tally for the Three Horns in W 712/3 (ITJ 750: 187). This analysis is confirmed by the use of the term in the OTC:

(1)

γuñ gī rjes la dags po γbañs su mñay ba las log go // (PT 1287: 203)

Thereafter, the Dags-po revolted from being possessed as subjects.

(2)

dags po γbañsu dgug pa γī dmag pon du bkay / (214) scal to // (PT 1287)

[The *bcan po*] appointed [Myi-čhen] as general by whom the Dags-po were to be subjected.

(3)

γuñ nas myi čhen gyis // dags po lha de la brgal te // dags po yoñs su bkug ste // (PT 1287: 214)

Thereafter, Myi-čhen, having fought against Lha-de [of] the Dags-po, completely subjected the Dags-po.

These quotations prove that Dags-po referred to a group of people that could be made subjects (*γbañs*). It seems also to have been used for the whole population and not just for males. According to the OTC, Dags-po were subjugated during the lifetime of Slon-bcan, the father of Khri Sroñ-rcan. Their inclusion into the administrative structures of the Empire was accomplished with issuing of the red tallies in S 718/9 (ITJ 750: 208).¹⁵

9 Dags-yul (#589) ‘Dags-po land’

(Uray 1960a: 206–7) Diese Landschaft lag östlich von Xol-kha und Yar-luñ am nördlichen oder an den beiden Ufern des Gcañ-po und ist im wesentlichen mit dem heutigen Dwags-po identisch. [...] der Lehnstaat Dags-po fiel zwischen 714 und 718 dem Geschlechte Mčhims zum Opfer; (Uray 1988a: 1504) is known from pre-eleventh century literature and documents in the forms of Dags, Dags-yul, Dags-śul and mainly of Dags-po; in the 16th–18th centuries supplanted by the spelling Dwags-po.

The toponym *dags yul* (< **dags poyi yul*) refers to the region inhabited by the Dags-po whose ruler held the title *da rgyal* ‘king of the Dags-po’.

¹⁵ The title of the ruler of the Dags-po, *da rgyal* ‘the king of the Dags-po’ (see OTD), is used in the OTA for the last time in W 714/5 (ITJ 750: 196), which might indicate that soon thereafter (e.g., in 718/9) the community lost the right to use the title and so to have their own ruler.

📍 **Dar-khwa-hywan (#61)**

Ch. stronghold captured in S 741/2 (ITJ 750: 285).

📍 **Diñ-diñ-tań (#73)**

Located in Ba-čos residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ in S 730/1 and S 732/3 (ITJ 750: 256, 262).

📍 **Du-gul (#81)**

Place where great councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcañ Yul-zuñ carried out the administration of the Žań-žuñ in 662/3 (PT 1288: 41); probably located outside of the Four Horns.

📍 **Duñs (#82)**

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ in S 717/8 (ITJ 750: 203). Places related: Mkhay-bu (council site in S 720/1) and Stag-cal (council site in W 673/4; residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ in S 720/1 and S 721/2).

👤 **Dur-gyis (#358)**

Western Turkic Türgiř people whose emissaries paid homage in S 732/3 and in S 744/5 (ITJ 750: 263, 297).

👤 **Dur-gyis kha gan (#775)**

Dur-gyis (Turk. Türgiř) *kha gan* (OTurk. *qayan*) married to *je ba* Ṳdron-ma-lod in 734/5.

📍 **Dold (#74)**

Region including Mar-ma (ITJ 750: 130); valley entrance: N 29°14'24.58, E 91°5'54.29.

📍 **Dra (#77)**

Identified with CT Grwa-nañ (Ch. Zānáng 扎囊; valley entrance: N 29°15'5.02, E 91°20'6.03). Places related: Gro-pu (council site of S 695/6 and S 718/9), Zar-phu (council site of S 719/20), and Bye-gro (council site of W 747/8).

📍 **Dra-bye (#75)**

Council site of W 745/6 (ITJ 750: 301). Could be identical with Bye-gro of Dra (?) since both Bye-gro of Dra and Dra-bye were winter council sites when the *bcan po* resided in Brag-mar.

📍 **Dra-cal (#76)**

Located in Skyi council site of W 712/3 (ITJ 750: 186).

📍 **Drib-nag (#78)**

Council site in S 722/3 and S 723/4 (ITJ 750: 224, 227).

📍 **Dru-gu** 'Western Turks'

📍 **Dru-gu-gu-zan-yul (#80)** 'Dru-gu-gu-zan land'

(Fleet 1914: 381): in one of the Tibetan works dealing with Li-yul or Khotan we have the name Gu-zan which can only be a transliteration of Gushān, Kushān; TLTD.2: 269: Dru-gu Gu-zan country; p. 282: Gu-zan was in the Dru-gu country; The name Gu-zan is highly suggestive of Guchen [...] it was the capital of what the Chinese designated Posterior Chū-shih, Anterior Chū-shih being Turfan itself; TLTD.3: 77: Possibly it might also have included Kuca, by reason of the original linguistic affinity; p. 78: This possibility would be enhanced if there were evidence for use of the name Kuşan (whence in that case might have come Gu-zan) in application to the joint region; in regard to the Turfan region the case is stronger; while it might thus seem probable that the name Kuşana clung to the Turfan-Ghu-chen area and gave rise to Gu-zan; TLTD.4: 46:a town in the T'ien shan, = Gu-chen, Pei t'ing, Beshaliq; (Harmatta 1969: 411): the Tibetan denomination of Gandhāra and Udyāna, territories of the Kuşāna Empire adjacent to Tibet, which then was transferred to the denomination of the country of the Turk Śāhis; (Uray 2007 [1979]: 120f.): either Kučā (Turk. Kūsen) or the former Kuşāna countries Gandhāra and Udyāna, governed by the Turk Śāhi dynasty; (Beckwith 1993: 50): the kingdom of Kucha; (Dotson 2009b: 96): Kucha; (Zeisler 2010: 393, fn. 25): Gu-zan might refer to Guchen in the eastern Tianshan north of Turfan, rather than to Kucha.

Dru-gu-gu-zan-yul is a metacompound¹⁶ of the underlying structure **dru guyi gu zan gyi yul*, lit. 'the land of Gu-zan of the Western Turks'. In 687/8 Tibetans launched a military campaign against the Dru-gu-gu-zan land:

(1)

(97) *pagī lo la bab ste / bcan po ñen kar na bźugs sīñ / blon khri ybrīñ gyis / dru gu gu zan yul du drañs /* (ITJ 750)

In the swine year, while the *bcan po* was abiding in Ñen-kar, [grand] councillor [Mgar] Khri-ybrīñ [Bcan-brod] drew to the Dru-gu-gu-zan land.¹⁷

(Harmatta 1969: 410f.) traced back OLT Gu-zan to the name Kuşāna, identifying it with the territories of Gandhāra and Udyāna under the rule of the 2nd Turk Śāhi dynasty.¹⁸ Close

¹⁶ On metacompounds, see (Bialek 2018a.1: 161ff.)

¹⁷ The preceding entry for the year 686/7 relates that a summer campaign of councillor Mgar Khri-ybrīñ Bcan-brod to the Dru-gu land was postponed. This might suggest that Dru-gu-yul in 686/7 was identical with Dru-gu-gu-zan-yul of 687/8. Councillor Mgar Khri-ybrīñ Bcan-brod came back from the Dru-gu (!) land after two years, in S 689/90. This would be another instance of the equivalence of Dru-gu-yul and Dru-gu-gu-zan-yul. The identity of the Dru-gu land with the Dru-gu-gu-zan land in these years was assumed by (Beckwith 1980a: 33 & 36, fn. 22). It is obvious that these events do not concern the region of Kucha for there is absolutely no reason why Kucha should have been perceived by Tibetans as part of the Dru-gu land, i.e. the territories of the Western Turks.

¹⁸ The account of the Korean pilgrim Hyecho composed between 723 and 729 does not mention Tibetans when reporting on the Turkic dynasty of Gandhāra and Udyāna ((Fuchs 1938: 444ff.); Gandhāra came under Turk rule in 625; (Harmatta 1969: 404)). We can therefore assume that the Tibetan conquest was either short-lived or aimed at imposing tribute but left the local dynasty on the throne. The second option appears more probable and is supported by the analogous Tibetan practices known from the occupied Khotan, where the local system of administration was retained (Takeuchi 2004b: 55), and from Arab sources where on the occasion of conquering Kabul between 812 and 815 we read: 'A king from among the kings of Tibet became a Muslim.' (*apud* (Beckwith 1993: 161)).

relations between Gandhāra and Tibet also continued in later times. Fromo Kesaro, who ruled Gandhāra in 739–46, has been perpetuated in Tibetan folklore as the hero Phrom Ge-sar (Harmatta and Litvinskij 1996: 382), and Buddhist scholars from Gandhāra visited Tibet in the 8th century. The Turk *ṣāhis* of Kābul were conceived of by Arabs as Tibetan vassals even at the beginning of the 9th century, i.e. in the period immediately preceding the Arab conquest ((Beckwith 1980a: 35); (Beckwith 1993: 161)).

The identification of Dru-gu-gu-zan with Gandhāra and Udyāna has yet another implication: by the year 687 (cf. ITJ 750: 97), Tibetans must have conquered and controlled large territories northwest of the *Žaṅ-žuṅ* territories and Ladakh in order to be able to supply their army on this new front. According to Inaba, “[i]n the 680s a prince from Kābul fled southward down to Zābulistān, probably due to the conflict surrounding succession to the throne, and established his independence there” (Inaba 2005: 2). His escape could have been caused by the Tibetan military campaign to the Dru-gu-gu-zan land in 687 and the stay of grand councillor Mgar Khri-γbriṅ Bcan-brod there until 689/90 (ITJ 750: 103). The following scenario seems plausible: Tibetans, allied with Western Turks (OLT *dru gu*) of Tokhāristān in conquering Chinese-controlled Tarim Basin (Beckwith 1980a: 32), independently attacked polities ruled by other Turkic dynasties south of Hindukush. These campaigns might have initially been led by councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu (676/7 to the Dru-gu land) and later by Mgar Khri-γbriṅ Bcan-brod (687/8 to the Dru-gu-gu-zan land).¹⁹ As a consequence of the military campaign of 687 the ruler of Kābul (also reigning over Gandhāra; (Inaba 2005: 2)), dethroned by the Tibetans, fled to Zābulistān and a new ruler, dependent on the Tibetans, was installed on the throne. This political coup would explain not only the longer sojourn of Mgar Khri-γbriṅ Bcan-brod in the Dru-gu-gu-zan land, but also the fact that the OTA use the verb *draṅs* (connoting military campaigns) in connection with the Dru-gu land – an unfathomable paradox in case the latter toponym would have only denoted Tokhāristān, with which Tibetans were allied. It seems therefore that in OLT Dru-gu-yul was a more general term denoting any polity ruled by a Western Turk (Dru-gu) dynasty;²⁰ Tibetans were allied only with one of those – the dynasty of Tokhāristān.

Beckwith concluded that the rulers of Kābul must have been Tibetan vassals at that time (ibid., p. 162). This also explains why Indian Buddhists from these regions (e.g., Padmasambhava from Udyāna) and from Kashmir were willingly visiting Central Tibet in the 8th century (Jettmar 1977: 421f.) – the regions remained under Tibetan control from the late 7th century. Obligated to pay tributes, the local Turk dynasty and the system of public administration might have been left, and so also Hyecho’s account is correct.

¹⁹ We notice that in the year preceding the first campaign, i.e. in 675, Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu ‘having prepared the administration of the *Žaṅ-žuṅ* people at Gu-rand of *Žims*, went to the Dru-gu-land ?as a *Itaṅ yo*/for *Itaṅ yo*?’ (ITJ 750: 64). The exact meaning and function of the phrase *Itaṅ yor* in the sentence are not known but it is obviously related to the military campaign that was launched a year later. What is relevant is the fact that councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu left for the campaign from the *Žaṅ-žuṅ* territories; there would be no reason for him to start the campaign from there if he were to attack Kucha or Guchen.

²⁰ Cf. “[...] we must regard Dru-gu-yul as the land of the Western Turks, in the broadest sense of the word. In fact, by Dru-gu-yul not only the habitations of the ‘Ten Tribes’ north and south of the T’ien-

A necessary prerequisite for a conquest of any Turk-ruled polity were reliable and well secured supply lines for the fighting forces. This presupposes military bases and permanent civil settlements in Ladakh and Baltistan.²¹ The strategic importance of Ladakh and Baltistan – the gates to north-west India and the Pamirs – brought about purposeful colonisation of the regions to help controlling the newly subjugated territories. This aim was achieved between 640s/650s (i.e. between the conquest of the *Žaṅ-žuṅ* and that of Kashgar in 663) and 687 when the attack on Gandhāra and Udyāna (Tib. Gu-zan) was launched. Military campaigns against other Western Turkic dynasties that Tibetans undertook in the 670s only support the hypothesis that Ladakh and Baltistan remained in Tibetan hands.²²

📍 **Dru-gu-yul (#354)** ‘Dru-gu (i.e. Western Turks) land’

📍 **Dron (#79)**

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in 705/6, S 706/7, S 707/8, S 708/9, 733/4, S 734/5, S 735/6, S 738/9, and place where the son Lhas-bon died in S 739/40 (ITJ 750: 150, 156, 160, 166, 175, 265, 268, 271, 279, 281). Places related: Maṅ-ste-luṅ (residence of Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 735/6, 736/7, and 737/8).

📍 **Mdan (#196)**

Council site in W 678/9 (ITJ 750: 72); modern Ldan (Ch. Diǎn 典; valley entrance: N 29°40'31.11, E 91°24'43.27).

shan mountains can be understood, but also the Tarim basin and Feryāna, and eventually even Toḡaristān and Gandhāra” (Uray 2007 [1979]: 120).

²¹ The military campaign to Gu-zan in 687/8 proves that some time between 644 (the *Žaṅ-žuṅ* conquest) and 687/8 the Tibetans must have conquered the area around Skar-do. In the light of the above discussed historical facts, it is inconceivable to me how Skar-do could have been “an independent country at a time when Khotan was being threatened by the Tibetans.” (Denwood 2008: 7); and further: “At the time of the composition of *The Inquiry of Vimalaprabhā*, i.e. some time between 660 and 670, it is clear that both Khotan and Suvarṇagotra, as well as Skar-do, were independent of the Tibetans, while *Žaṅ-žuṅ* was not.” (ibid., p. 8; cf. also (Denwood 2009: 151)). In his analysis, Denwood relied on the dating of the composition of *The Inquiry of Vimalaprabhā* but did not present any independent evidence for the assumed date between 660 and 670 ((Denwood 2008: 8–9) (Denwood 2009: 151)). I doubt that *The Inquiry of Vimalaprabhā* was composed between 660 and 670. The text might have been written some time after the narrated events and the author, presenting them retrospectively, could have brought together in time situations that were divided by years in reality. For instance, the mention of the Sum-pa and the *Xa-ža* threatening Khotan would suggest a period preceding Tibetan conquest of these peoples and thus also the Tibetan occupation of Khotan by at least 30 years; for other inconsistencies in the plot see (Zeisler 2010: 420ff.) Therefore, the narrative relates to historical events (in a rather confounded manner) but is certainly not a historical document.

²² This hypothesis would also explain why in the imperial period none of these regions had to be reconquered by the Tibetans – neither Chinese nor Tibetan sources record any repeated military campaigns in Ladakh or Baltistan, as opposed, for instance, to the Great and Little Bolōr or the Pamirs.

📍 **Mdo-smad (#198)**

Region to the north-east of the Bod land administered separately by regularly convened councils. Places related: Rgyod, Ńas (Žo-thaŃ), GŃi-ji-gen, Nam-lđoŃ-prom, Par (Gle-ma), Dbu-le (Lha-ri-mo), Dbu-le-lam-nag, Dbu-siŃ-Ńag, ųbro-lčhiyu-luŃ, Gce, Gce-nam-yor, Zol, Yol (Či-ybos, Rteyu-dkyus), Rag-tag (Rma-roŃ, Ńam-pu), Re-kras-yjoŃ, Re-luŃ-bzaŃs, Ryam-si-gar, Seb, Sla-sod (Snig).

📍 **Mdo-bzer RcaŃ-khoŃ (#197)**

žaŃ and councillor proclaimed by the *bcan po* as army commander of the colonial government of Rma in 755/6 (Or.8212/187: 13–4, 15, 28, 34, 40–1, 69).

📍 **ųdoŃ-ka (#119)**

Region including Ne-co-luŃ (council site in S 673/4).

📍 **ųdron-ma-lod (#120)**

je ba sent as a bride for the *kha gan* of the Dur-gyis in S 734/5 (ITJ 750: 268).

📍 **Rdo ųphan-koŃ (#250)**

Appointed as *bruŃ pa* by the council in S 707/8; removed in S 714/5 (ITJ 750: 162, 194).

📍 **Ldu-nag (#170)**

Located in Zrid residence of *bcan po* Khri MaŃ-slon MaŃ-rcan in 665/6 and 669/70, and council site in S 728/9 (PT 1288: 45, 50; ITJ 750: 249); identical with modern ųdu-nag (Ch. Dųnàgǎng 杜纳岗; N 30°23'25.51, E 91°7'29.99).

📍 **Ldu-nag-slad-ma (#169)**

Located in Zrid residence of *bcan po* Khri MaŃ-slon MaŃ-rcan in 666/7 (PT 1288: 46); prob. upstream from Ldu-nag.

📍 **Ldum-bu-khri-bśos-khrom (#374)** ‘colonial province of Ldum-bu-khri-bśos’

BYD: 272b: mkhar gyi miŃ.

(Stein 1952: 84): Khri-bśos est le Kokonor et Ldum-bu est visiblement à rattacher à Bcan-sŃa Ldom-bu; (Dotson 2009b: 91): Khri-bśos Stronghold.

In later Tibetan sources and ethnographies, Khri-sog (for variant spellings see (Stein 1959: 195f.)) surfaces either as a name of the Kokonor lake (see e.g. (Stein 1959: 293f.); (Uray 1980: 313); (Kværne and Martin 2023: 104, fn. 91)) or part of its name like in Yutso Trishog Jelmo (LT prob. *yul cho khri sog rgyal mo*) ‘Lake of Ten Thousand Families, Queen of Lakes’ (Combe 1926: 169). (Stein 1959: 195) mentioned ruins considered to have been remains of a

castle of a certain king (*rgyal po*) Khrom Khri-śog and the word *khrom* recurs in later records in different connections with Khri-śog.

The expression *ldum bu khri bśos khrom* can only be analysed in one of two ways:

1. **ldum bu [khri bśos]_{APP} kyi khrom*, lit. 'colonial province of *ldum bu* Khri-bśos'; here *ldum bu* would denote either an edifice called Khri-bśos (cf. *mkhar phrag* in ITJ 750: 221, 225, 257) or a settlement of the same name
2. **ldum bu khri bśos kyi khrom*, lit. 'colonial province of Ldum-bu Khri-bśos'

Since the gloss 'mkhar' for *ldum bu* is only provided by one source without any further textual evidence, I consider it contextual and therefore doubtful. Instead, I propose connecting *ldum bu* to *dum* 'black; blue; dark' attested thus far only in Kuki-Chin languages (STEDT #4062). The same root occurs in OLT *ldum* 'vegetables, greens', likewise attested in the variant form *ldum bu* (see OTDO). I think that Ldum-bu was a Tibetan name for the Kokonor lake, naming it by its colour, like all neighbouring non-Tibetic speaking communities did (cf. also later LT Mcho-sñon), lit. 'A Little Dark-Blue One'.²³ That written Tibetic languages did not distinguish between blue and green is confirmed by the word *sño* 'blue; green'. *ldum* denoted any kind of dark colour in the spectrum of black, blue, and green. The meaning of *khri bśos* remains unclear by it doubtlessly formed part of the proper name, maybe as its attribute. Thus, Ldum-bu-khri-bśos-khrom denoted the colonial province (*khrom*) that included the Kokonor lake.

♣ Sdag-čuñ-bjañ (#286)

A petitioner from Kwa-ču (Or.8212/187: 87).

📍 Sdiñs (#507)

Located in Zu-spug residence of *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan's court in S 761/2 (Or.8212/187: 41). The name may be preserved in Ch. Dīnglǎng 丁朗 (N 29°40'31.71, E 91°49'25.55) located in a valley identified with OLT Zu-spug.

²³ It is generally assumed that the OLT onset LD- is an outcome of γ - [N-] prefixed to a liquid root onset: *N₊L- > *N₊DL > *DL- > LD-. This process however applies to verbs and has so far not been documented for nouns. Even if the presumed connection to the KC *dum* should prove false, the explanation of Ldum-bu as referring to Kokonor remains valid via *ldum* 'greens'.

n

📍 Na-mar (#221)

Council site in S 706/7 and residence of Khri Lde-gcug-rcaṅ's court in S 746/7 and 747/8 (ITJ 750: 157, 303, 307; Or.8212/187: 7, 10). Called *pho braṅ* in 746/7 but this most probably results from a scribal error, cf.:

(1)

(303) § / *khyī lo la / bcaṅ po dbyard pho braṅ na mar na bźugs* / (ITJ 750)

In the dog year, in the summer, the *bcaṅ po* abode in the castle Na-mar.

👤 Na-ri-ba-ba (#544)

Narendradeva, a Nepalese (OLT Bal-po) king in exile in Tibet after Yu-sna-kug-ti (Skt. *Jiṣṇagupta* or *Viṣṇugupta*) had usurped the throne in 631; re-installed on the throne by the Tibetans in 642/3 (PT 1288: 12; (Bialek 2018c: 23)).

📍 Nam-ldoṅ-prom (#224)

Mdo-smad council site in W 702/3 (ITJ 750: 140).

📍 Nam-ce-gliṅ (#223)

Residence of *bcaṅ po* Khri Maṅ-slon-maṅ-rcaṅ in W 672/3 (ITJ 750: 54); possibly identical with CT Gnam-gliṅ in Śaṅs (N 29°40'56.12, E 89°5'55.98).

📍 Nubs (#230)

Located in Ḫo-yug council site of W 715/6 (ITJ 750: 200).

📍 Ne-co-luṅ (#227)

Located in Ḫdoṅ-ka council site in S 673/4 and S 760/1 (ITJ 750: 57; Or.8212/187: 39).

👤 Gnubs Kho-ma-re (#102)

bruṅ pa; died in S 707/8 (ITJ 750: 161).

👤 Gnubs Khri-mñen Mon-can (#103)

Grand *khud pa*; died in W 713/4 (ITJ 750: 191–2).

👤 Gnubs Khri-sum-rje Stag-rcaṅ (#104)

Installed as a *mñan* in S 723/4 (ITJ 750: 228–9).

📍 **Gnubs Mañ-ñen Bži-brcan (#105)**

Councillor; active between 681/2 and 696/7 (ITJ 750: 79, 82, 98, 116, 118, 124).

📍 **Mnon (#212)**

Council site in W 714/5 (ITJ 750: 196). It may be identical with the later Snon, nowadays Rgya-ma valley (valley entrance: 29°48'1.20"N, 91°39'26.96"E), the home territory of the Mnon family (Hazod 2014).

📍 **Mnon Snañ-grags (#211)**

Instigator; together with Khe-rgad Mdo-snañ revolted in 705/6 and was executed at Bon-mo-na-la-ce (ITJ 750: 151).

📍 **Rnañ-po-ñur-myig (#271)**

Residence of Khri-ma-lod in S 703/4 and of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ in S 721/2 (ITJ 750: 144, 219).

📍 **Rnams (#272)**

Located in (Lower) Skyi council site of W 711/2 (ITJ 750: 181) and W 743/4 (ITJ 750: 294; Or.8212/187: 1–2); valley entrance: N 29°27'37.93, E 90°55'3.60.

📍 **Sna-bo (#305)**

Located in Xon residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcañ in W 675/6 (ITJ 750: 65); modern Nàbù 纳布 (N 29°18'5.26, E 91°48'51.75).

📍 **Sna-riñs (#306)**

Located in Sñiñ-druñ place of residence of grand councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcañ Yul-zuñ in 658/9 (PT 1288: 35).

📍 **Snam-stod (#308)**

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcañ in 663/4 (PT 1288: 43).

📍 **Snig (#310)**

Located in Sla-śod site of a Mdo-smad council in S 764/5 (Or.8212/187: 57, 63).

p

1 Pa-gor Na-ydod (#231)

An official mentioned in W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 21).

9 Pa-noñ (#232)

Region (possibly within the former Žaň-žuň territory) including Čhos-goň (council site in S 724/5).

1 Pa-cab Gyim-po (#420)

Servant (*bran*) of Myaň Žaň-snaň (PT 1287: 313–4). When the latter became disloyal to *bcan po* Khri Sroň-rcan, Pa-cab Gyim-po overthrew Myaň Žaň-snaň and destroyed his residence Sñur-ba (PT 1288: 4–5).

1 Pa-cab Rgyal-can Thom-po (#741)

Together with Mgar Xbriň-rcan Rcaň-rton prepared sheaves of the Left Horn in W 690/1 (ITJ 750: 106–7).

9 Par (#233)

Region located in Mdo-smad. Related place: Gle-ma (council site in W 706/7).

9 Poň-khri-mu-steňs (#240)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroň in S 702/3 (ITJ 750: 139).

9 Poň-lag-raň (#241)

Place where the elder brother Lha-bal-pho was deposed from the throne in 705/6 (ITJ 750: 152).

9 Pyi-cal (#242)

Located in Skyi council site in W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 19).

1 Spug Gyim-rcan Rma-čhuň (#316)

Installed as *mñan* of the Žaň-žuň land in 653/4; messenger of Khri Sroň-rcan to Sad-mar-kar (PT 1287: 402–7; PT 1288: 25).

♣ **Spuñ-rye-ryuñ** (#317)

Lord (*rje*) of the Ra-saṅ; together with Khu Khri-sña Dgru-zuñ accused in W 678/9; his wealth was appraised in 680/1 (ITJ 750: 72, 75); id. with Sña-śur Spuñs-rye-rgyug?

📍 **Spel** (#314)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcaṅ in S 724/5 (ITJ 750: 232).

📍 **Sprags** (#315)

Region (north-eastern part of modern Ṃdam-gzuñ county, Ch. Dāngxióng 当雄) including Murgas and Śa-ra.

ph

📍 Phar (#234)

Place of *bcan po* Khri Ḳdus-sroṅ's sojourn in W 698/9 (ITJ 750: 128), from where he went to Briḡu-taṅ of Bal-po in S 699/700 (ITJ 750: 129).

📍 Phu-čuṅ (#237)

Located in Glag council site of W 674/5, W 685/6, W 694/5, Sp 701/2, S 756/7, S 762/4, S 764/5 (ITJ 750: 61, 92, 118, 137; Or.8212/187: 18, 46, 56, 62, 75).

📍 Phud-gon (#238)

A fortress in the vicinity of stronghold Ĵid-par.

📍 Phul-po (#239)

Region including Ńa-śa-chal (council site of W 689/90).

📍 Pho-dam-mdo (#235)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Maṅ-slon Maṅ-rcan in early S 673/4 (ITJ 750: 56). Most probably located in Śaṅs for the *bcan po* stayed in W 672/3 in Nam-ce-gliṅ of Śaṅs, in early summer 673/4 in Pho-dam-mdo, and in late summer 673/4 in Sum-ču-bo of Śaṅs. Could be identical with modern Pàmăduō 帕玛多 (N 29°35'46.42, E 89° 3'56.32) in Śaṅs.

(Hazod 2009: 217) identified Pho-dam-mdo with modern Phod-mdo in the Byaṅ district of Lhun-grub country (cf. also TTT #353; 25.07.2023). This location seems problematic in view of the events described in the OTA. The following sites hosted the *bcan po* or his court in the respective periods:

<i>bcan po</i>	S 672/3	Sum-ču-bo of Śaṅs
<i>bcan po</i>	W 672/3	Nam-ce-gliṅ (of Śaṅs) ²⁴
<i>bcan po</i>	S 673/4	Pho-dam-mdo
<i>bcan po</i>	S 673/4	Sum-ču-bo (of Śaṅs)
<i>pho braṅ</i>	W 673/4	Rab-ka-cal of Śaṅs

In the periods preceding and following the early summer of 673/4, the *bcan po* or his court were staying in the Śaṅs district. It can be therefore be reasonably argued that Pho-dam-mdo was also located in this area of the Right Horn.

²⁴ I bracket Śaṅs if it is not explicitly mentioned in the text but has been located on other grounds.

📍 **Phyiñ-ba** (#243)

Valley in which the royal necropolis was located (PT 1288: 17, 19; ITJ 750: 74, 158, 190) identical with modern ᚱphyoñ-rgyas; cemetery: N 29°1'3.11, E 91°40'54.49.

📍 **Phrag** (#236)

Castle and council site in W 721/2, W 722/3 and W 730/1 (ITJ 750: 221, 225, 257).

b

📍 **Ba-mgo (#16)**

Stronghold (?) located in Khar-can and captured together with Keyu-śan by councillor Skyes-bzañ in W 761/2 (Or.8212/187: 44, 73). Identified with Ch. Pānhé 番禾, a district under the administration of Liangzhou (see s.v. Leñ-ču) by (Rong 1990: 262).

(Baxter and Sagart 2014) (Schuessler 2007)

pān 番
hé 禾

MC *hwa*
OC *[G]^hoj

LH *ɣuai/guai*
OCM *(g)wâi

Although the MC values of *pān* 番 have not been reconstructed, there is no reason to assume that its final was *-m*. Since !Ban-go would perfectly conform to the orthographic rules of OLT and no internal motivation exists for *-m* > *-n* / *_g*^[+velar], Rong's proposal requires further support to be accepted, especially as he himself noticed that the official name of Pānhé was changed already in 744 to Tiānbǎo 天寶 (ibid., fn. 43).

📍 **Ba-čhos (#14)**

Region including Diñ-diñ-tañ.

📍 **Ba-bams (#13)**

Council site in W 680/1 (ITJ 750: 76) and residence of the court in S 757/8 (Or.8212/187: 24). Places related: G.yag-ru-goñ (residence of the court in S 757/8) and G.yag-ru-thañ (council site in W 680/1).

📍 **Ba-lam (#15)**

Valley where the body of Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcañ was kept in 677/8–678/9 (ITJ 750: 69, 71) before being buried; valley entrance: N 29°39'12.10, E 91°22'46.99.

📍 **Bañ-mo-bañ-kar (#17)**

Place where councillor Mgar Khri-ɣbrin Bcañ-brod was installed as great councillor in 685/6 (ITJ 750: 91).

📍 **Ban-ɣjag nag-po (#20) 'Black Ban-ɣjag'**

A people from the Upper Regions (*stod phyogs*) who paid homage in W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 20). Preserved possibly in KhG as Ban-pa: *ban pa rje ɣa ʒa rje / drañ gar rje / zin po rje / ʒañ ʒuñ rje nams btul/* (Xphreñ-ba 1962: 11v4) '[Stag-ri Gñan-gzigs] subdued the lord of the Ban-pa, the lord of the ʒa-ʒa, the lord of the Drañ-gar, Zin-po-rje, [and] the lord of the ʒañ-ʒuñ.'

📍 ¹Bal-po (#18)

Residence of *bcan pos* in S 675/6, S 690/1, S 695/6, 697/8, S 707/8, 709/10, 710/1, S 711/2, S 712/3, 718/9, S 719/20, S 722/3 and S 723/4 (ITJ 750: 63, 104, 119, 125, 160, 166, 171, 175, 179, 184, 207, 210, 224, 227). Places related: Briyu-taṅ (residence of Khri Ḫdus-sroṅ in S 699/700; council site of S 725/6) and Śa-ru-mkhar (residence of Khri Lde-gcug-rcaṅ in S 708/9). (Hazod 2009: 172) identified Bal-po with Dpal/Bal-sde/Sbal-luṅ of north-western Yar-ḡbrog in Left Horn.

👤 ²Bal-po (#19) 'Nepalese'

📍 Bum-liṅ (#36)

Place where *žaṅ* Rgyal-zigs and *žaṅ* Stoṅ-rcaṅ crossed a branch bridge and captured many Ch. strongholds in 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 51, 81, 82, 83).

📍 Bur (#37)

Located in Skyi (south of Sñe-thaṅ) council site in W 761/2 and W 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 43, 47, 72, 78); valley entrance: N 29°31'27.45, E 90°55'33.95.

📍 Beg (#24)

Located outside of the Bod land destination of Khri Lde-gcug-rcaṅ's military campaign in S 739/40 (ITJ 750: 281).

📍 Bog-la (#27)

Mountain pass, from which Gnubs Maṅ-ñen Bži-brcaṅ and Mgar Maṅ-žam Stag-cab came down and convened the council at Luṅ-riṅs of Rgyas in S 681/2 (ITJ 750: 79).

👤 Bod (#26) 'Bod; a people of Tibetan descent native to the Four Horns (*ru bži*)'

📍 Bod-yul (#25) 'Bod land'

In the OTA, coextensive with the Three and then the Four Horns.

📍 Bon-mo-na-la-ce (#29)

Place where the instigators Mnon Snaṅ-grags and Khe-rgad Mdo-snaṅ were killed in 705/6 (ITJ 750: 151).

📍 Bol-gaṅs (#28)

Located in Mcho-bgo outside of the Bod land residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcaṅ in S 728/9 (ITJ 750: 248).

📍 **Bya-cal (#38)**

Located in Sgreys council site of W 738/9 (ITJ 750: 280).

📍 **Byar (#40)**

Region including ¹Lčañ-bu (residence of *bcan po*'s court in W 758/9, W 761/2, W 762/3, and 764/5).

📍 **Byar-liñs-cal (#39)**

Located in Skyi council site in W 703/4, W 704/5, W 728/9, and W 746/7 (ITJ 750: 149, 250, 304; Or.8212/187: 7; Dx 12851v: 3).

📍 **Bye-gro (#41)**

Located in Dra council site of W 747/8 (Or.8212/187: 10); identical with Dra-bye (? cf. ITJ 750: 301). Both Bye-gro and Dra-bye were winter council sites when the *bcan po* resided in Brag-mar. (Dotson 2009b: 128) read Rce-gro.

📍 **Bye-ma-luñ (#42)**

Located in Lha-gab council site of S 712/3 (ITJ 750: 185).

📍 **Bra-ma-thañ (#30)**

Located in Skyi council site of W 686/7 and W 691/2 (ITJ 750: 95, 109). Bra-ma-thañ and Bra-ma-tañ of Skyi (understood as relating to the same place) have tentatively been identified by Hazod with modern Skyi-dra-cal (Hazod 2009: 217).

📍 **Brag-sgo (#32)**

Council site of S 704/5 (ITJ 750: 147).

📍 **Brag-mar (#31)**

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ in W 695/6 and of Khri Lde-gcug-rčan in W 707/8, W 708/9, W 709/10, W 710/11, W 711/2, W 712/3, W 713/4, W 717/8, W 718/9, W 719/20, W 721/2, W 722/3, W 723/3, W 724/5, W 725/6, W 726/7, W 728/9, W 730/1, W 736/7, W 737/8, W 738/9, W 740/1, W 741/2, W 743/4, W 744/5, W 745/6, W 746/7, W 747/8 (ITJ 750: 120, 163, 168, 172, 177, 180, 186, 190, 204, 208, 212, 221, 225, 229, 234, 237, 240, 249, 257, 275, 277, 279, 284, 286, 294, 298, 300, 303; Or.8212/187: 1, 6, 7, 10); place where *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-lde-brčan was born in 742/3 (ITJ 750: 291); valley entrance: N 29°19'57.41, E 91°30'34.16. Places related: Cal-ka (court's residence in W 697/8), Dbu-chal (residence in W 729/30), and Xom-bu-cal (residence in W 731/2, W 732/3, W 733/4, W 734/5, and W 735/6).

📍 **Briyu-taṅ (#34)**

Located in Bal-po residence of *bcan po* Khri Ḳdus-sroṅ in S 699/700 and council site in S 725/6 (ITJ 750: 129, 236).

👤 **Bru-ža (#350)**

A people of Little Bolör (Gilgit) conquered by councillor Ḳbal Skyes-bzaṅ Ldoṅ-cab in 737/8 but lost in S 747/8. Their king (*rgyal po*; Mǎláixī 馬來兮 according to Ch. sources) paid homage in W 737/8 and his successor (*bru ža rje*; Sūshīlīzhī 蘇失利之 according to Ch. sources) received *je ba* Khri-ma-lod as bride in S 740/1 (ITJ 750: 276, 277, 283; Or.8212/187: 10).

📍 **Bru-ža-yul (#349)** 'Bru-ža land'

📍 **Breṅ (#33)**

Council site of S 743/4 (ITJ 750: 294).

👤 **Dbays Skyes-bzaṅ Stag-snaṅ (#301)**

Overthrew Ba-mgo and Keyu-śan of Khar-can in W 761/2; fought against the Ch. general Hon Je-saṅs at Ḳguy-log-sgaṅ (cf. PT 1287: 378; Or.8212/187: 9, 32–3, 36, 44).

👤 **Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaṅ-ñen (#62)**

Proclaimed as grand councillor in W 705/6; died in S 721/2 (ITJ 750: 155, 157, 161, 164, 167, 169, 180, 181–2, 184–5, 187, 189, 191, 193, 197, 200, 203, 205, 209, 214, 220).

👤 **Dbays Khri-sum-rje Rcaṅ-bžer (#63)**

Councillor (active from 713/4) proclaimed as grand councillor in W 721/2; died in S 725/6 (ITJ 750: 192, 196, 198, 200, 204, 207, 210, 213, 216, 217, 221, 223, 224, 225, 227, 230, 233, 234–5, 236, 237).

👤 **Dbays Stag-sgra Khoṅ-lod (#65)**

Proclaimed as grand councillor in W 727/8 but dismissed in W 728/9 (ITJ 750: 241, 245, 249).

👤 **Dbays Snaṅ-bžer Zla-brcan (#64)**

Grand councillor from approx. 756/7 to 764/5; overthrew the Chinese strongholds Great Coṅ-ka and Seg-śiṅ-kun in W 757/8 and was bestowed a letter of *ke ke ru* in S 764/5 (Or.8212/187: 23, 25, 28, 30, 39, 59, 64).

♣ **Dbays Sum-po-skyes (#66)**

Indulged in an accusation in S 727/8 (ITJ 750: 243).

📍 **Dbu-chal (#67)**

Located in Brag-mar court's residence in W 729/30 (ITJ 750: 253).

📍 **Dbu-ru-śod (#70)**

Region including Re-skam (council site in 684/5) and Lčiŷu-luñ (council site in S 724/5).

📍 **Dbu-le (#69)**

Located in Mdo-smad council site of S 759/60 (Or.8212/187: 35); possibly a larger region, within which Lam-nag (see Dbu-le-lam-nag) was located. Places related: Lha-ri-mo (council site of S 762/4).

📍 **Dbu-le-lam-nag (#68)**

Mdo-smad council site in S 755/6 (Or.8212/187: 14); possibly identical with Dbu-le.

📍 **Dbu-śiñ-ñag (#71)**

Located in Mdo-smad council site of S 758/9 (Or.8212/187: 31).

♣ **Xbay da śi (#515)**

A foreign emissary who paid homage in W 700/1 (ITJ 750: 134). His provenance is not stated in the OTA but Petech reconstructed the assumed Chinese form of his name as Mǎ 馬/Má 麻 dà(i)-shǐ 大使 (Petech 1988a: 281). The title dà(i)-shǐ can be translated as 'envoy'.

♣ **Xbay cañ kun (#113)**

Chinese general who led Chinese military troops of the Kog land in 745/6 (Or.8212/187: 4). *cañ kun* is a transcription of Ch. *jiāng-jūn* 将军 'general'.

♣ **Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab (#469)**

A councillor between 729/30 (ITJ 750: 252) and 746/7 (ITJ 750: 304) responsible for: committing a battle against the Chinese at Mu-le-ču-le in 729/30 (ITJ 750: 252); sacking Khyi-śa-čan in 734/5 (ITJ 750: 270); drawing towards Bru-ža land in 737/8 (ITJ 750: 276); convening a council at Śo-ma-ra of Skyi and administering soldiers in 744/5 (ITJ 750: 298-9; Or.8212/187: 3); convening a council at Byar-liñs-cal of Skyi and administering summer pastures and straw-lands of the Four Horns in 746/7 (ITJ 750: 304-5; Or.8212/187: 7-8); and convening a council at Bye-gro of Dra and making the account of summer pastures and straw-lands in 747/8 (Or.8212/187: 10-1).

Served as great councillor after Xbro Čuñ-bzañ Xor-mañ and was replaced by Dbays Snañ-bzer Zla-brtsan (PT 1287: 112). The OTA-II record the confiscation of Xbal's and Lañ's possessions and the banishment of their servants to Mtoñ-sod in the year 755/6 (Or.8212/187: 12–6). The Žol inscription gives disloyalty as the reason for the accusations (Žol S 5–17), suggesting that Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab together with Lañ Myes-zigs were responsible for the death of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan and threatened his successor *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan.

Dbays Snañ-bzer Zla-brcan is called councillor in W 756/7 (Or. 8212/187: 23) but great councillor in 757/8 (Or.8212/187: 25). Because in 755/6 Xbal's possessions were confiscated one may assume that he remained great councillor only until this year. In Or.8212/187: 10–1, the following persons are said to have convened the winter council: great councillor(s) [Xbro] Čuñ-bzañ [Xor-mañ] and Xbal [Skyes-bzañ] Ldoñ-cab, councillor Mañ-pho-rje, and Žañ Xbriñ-rcan. It seems plausible to read the title *blon če* as referring to both Xbro Čuñ-bzañ Xor-mañ and Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab. The next person mentioned in the list has the title *blon*. It would be unusual for a person without any title to be mentioned before a councillor. Thus, Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab might have replaced Xbro Čuñ-bzañ Xor-mañ as great councillor during the winter council of 747/8.

♦ Xbu-śiñ-kun (#117)

Ch. stronghold conquered by *žañ* Rgyal-zigs and *žañ* Stoñ-rcan in 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 52, 84).

♣ Xbug-čor (#365)

Eastern Turks; their emissary paid homage in 720/1. Ch. transcription *mòchuò* 默啜 was used with reference to Qap(a)ghan Qaghan who reigned over the Eastern Turks from 692 to 716 (Clauson 1957: 1-3); (Beckwith 1993: 58 & fn. 23).

	(Baxter and Sagart 2014)	(Schuessler 2007)
<i>mò</i> 默		LH <i>mək</i>
		OCM * <i>mək</i>
<i>chuò</i> 啜	MC <i>tsyhwet</i>	LH <i>tʂ^huat</i>
	OC * <i>t^hot</i>	OCM <i>thot</i> ?

♣ Xbriñ-rcan Khyi-bu (#114)

žañ; installed as equerry by the council in W 717/8 (ITJ 750: 205, 246; Or.8212/187: 11).

♣ Xbro Čuñ-bzañ Xor-mañ (#115)

Proclaimed as grand councillor in W 728/9; active between 728/9 and approx. 747/8 (ITJ 750: 249, 250, 254, 258, 260, 264, 266, 273, 293, 298, 303; Or.8212/187: 1, 3, 8, 10–1).

♦ Xbro-lchiyu-luñ (#116)

Mdo-smad council site in W 727/8 (ITJ 750: 247).

m

♀ **Mañ-ste-luñ** (#190)

Located in Dron residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rčan in S 735/6, 736/7, and 737/8 (ITJ 750: 271, 274, 276).

♂ **Mañ-pañs** (#188)

Prob. minor wife of Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rčan and mother of Lha-bal-pho; died in W 706/7 and was buried in A 707/8 (ITJ 750: 159, 162).

♂ **Mañ-po-rje** (#60)

King of the Dags-po (*da rgyal*) active between 653/4 and 659/60; died in the battle against Ch. general Seyu Den-pañ at Mcho-nag-stoñ-ru (PT 1288: 24, 37); prob. father of Khri-zuñ.

♂ **Mañ-mo-rje** (#187)

bcan mo (ITJ 750: 124).

♂ **Mañ-mo-rje Bži-steñ** (#186)

Mother of Khri Sroñ-lde-brčan, from the Sna-nam family; died in S 742/3 (PT 1286: 66–7; ITJ 750: 292).

♂ **Mañ-rčan Ldoñ-zi** (#545)

Councillor (ITJ 750: 140–1).

♂ **Mañ-rčan Xphan-gañ** (#189)

Councillor (Or.8212/187: 14–5, 26–7, 27).

♀ **Mar-ma** (#192)

Located in Dold residence of Khri Xdus-sroñ in W 699/700 (ITJ 750: 130).

♂ **Mard** (#193)

A people inhabiting Ladakh (CT *mar yul*) whose census (together with the Žañ-žuñ people) was carried out at Chañ-bañ-sna by *žañ* Bčan-to-re Lhas-byin and councillor Khri-sum-rje Rcañ-bzer in W 719/20 (ITJ 750: 213); prob. coreferential with Suvarṇagotra (Gser-rigs) and Ch. Mòluósuō 秣羅娑.

📍 **Mal-tro** (#191)

The name is preserved in modern Mal-gro-guñ-dkar (Ch. Mòzhúgōngkǎ 墨竹工卡; N 29°50'14.49, E 91°43'44.57). Places related: Ltams (council site in S 714/5), Brjen-tañ (residence of *bcan po* in 694/5, S 713/4, and S 714/5, and council site in S 761/2) and Ske-bye (residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in 660/1).

📍 **Mu-le-ču-le** (#216)

Battlefield where councillor Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab fought against the Chinese in S 729/30 (ITJ 750: 253).

👤 **Mun-čaṅ koñ čo** (#422)

Chinese princess married to Khri Sroñ-rcan. She is mentioned as *bcan mo* three times in the OTA: on the occasion of her coming to Tibet in 641/2 (PT 1288: 11–2), when *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan died (PT 1288: 15), and when her funeral was prepared in W 683/4 (ITJ 750: 85). Her name is a Tibetan transcription of Ch. name Wénchéng and the title *gongzhu* ‘imperial princess’ (Uray 1991: 199, fn. 26):

	(Baxter and Sagart 2014)		(Schuessler 2007)	
	MC	OC	LH	OCM
wén文	mjun	*mə[n]	mun	*mən
chéng成	dzyeng	[d]eŋ	dzeŋ	geŋ ?
gōng公	kuwng	*C.q'oŋ	koŋ	*kōŋ
zhǔ主	tsyuX	toʔ	tso	toʔ

📍 **Mur-gas** (#217)

Located in Sprags council site in S 680/1 and S 683/4 (ITJ 750: 76, 84–5).

📍 **Mer-khe** (#199)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in 650/1, 654/5–658/9, and 661/2 (PT 1288: 18, 27, 29, 31, 33, 35, 40); modern Mer-khe-če (valley entrance: N 30°17'13.95, E 91°9'1.37). The body of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ was kept in Mer-khe prior to the funeral in W 706/7 (ITJ 750: 153, 156).

📍 **Moñ** (#215)

Valley in Upper Stod where the residence of Khri-ma-lod in S 701/2 and council site in S 757/8 were located (ITJ 750: 136; Or.8212/187: 25); valley entrance: N 29°58'59.09, E 90°43'55.17.

📍 **Moñ-kar** (#213)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ in S 700/1, and council site in W 713/4, W 717/8 and W 723/4 (ITJ 750: 132, 191, 204, 229); possibly located in Moñ.

📍 **Moñ-pu-sral-yjoñ (#214)**

Council site in 654/5 (PT 1288: 27) presumably located in Upper Moñ (*moñ pu*).

📍 **Myañ-sgrom (#219)**

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan's court in S 760/1 (Or.8212/187: 38–9).

👤 **Myañ X̣dus-khoñ (#218)**

Prob. councillor Myañ Snañ-bzañ X̣dus-khoñ, grandfather of *ban de* Myañ Tiñ-ñe-yjin (Žwa W 33); installed prob. as *bruñ pa* in W 745/6 (ITJ 750: 301–2).

👤 **Mywa (#782)**

(Chang 1959: 147): undoubtedly identical with the kingdom of Nan chao; (Richardson 1983: 136): it is possible that the Mywa of the eighth century were ancestors of the rather insignificant Miao people now found near the western borders of Szachwan and Yunnan; (Beckwith 1987: 65): a people corresponding in part to the Nan chao; fn. 64: seems to be an Old Tibetan transcription of the same ethnonym transcribed by the modern Chinese as Miao; (Petech 1988c: 1080): White Mywa and Black Mywa (Pai Man and Wu Man for the Chinese) were two districts in which X̣jañ was divided; (Beckwith 2003 [1983]: 280, fn. 10): a transcription of the name of the Yunnanese people known in Chinese transcription as the Miao; (Dotson 2009b: 103, fn. 220): The Mywa people correspond in part to the Nanzhao. They are divided into black and white Mywa. The white Mywa, corresponding to the Chinese Bai Man were more Sinicized, and formed the ruling class of the Nanzhao kingdom, which would be consolidated in the middle of the eighth century. The Black Mywa, or Wu Man, were an endogamous group corresponding apparently to the Yi (Lolo). They formed the majority of Nanzhao, but were far less Sinicized in their customs.

OLT *mywa* is a transcription either of Ch. *miáo*苗 or directly of the group's endonym. Table 1 provides the reconstructed values of the Chinese word:²⁵

	(Pulleyblank 1991)	(Baxter and Sagart 2014)
<i>miáo</i> 苗	Y. mjɛ́	MC <i>mjew</i>
	L. miaw	OC *m(r)aw
	E. miaw	

Table 1. Reconstruction of Chinese *miáo*苗

For the lack of the historical form of the endonym it is impossible to disambiguate the source of OLT *mywa*.

The name recurs in two OLT records, the OTA and the OTC, in five distinct formations:

1. Mywa (PT 1287: 345; ITJ 750: 148, 265)
2. White Mywa (*mywa dkar po*; PT 1287: 335, 343, 393)
3. Black Mywa (*mywa nag po*; PT 1287: 335; ITJ 750: 289)
4. X̣jañ-Mywa (PT 1287: 347)
5. Land of the Mywa (*mywa yul*; Dx 12851: v6)

The following quotations shall clarify the status of the demonyms as their were understood by the Tibetan elites of the Empire.

²⁵ (Schuessler 2007) does not contain the corresponding reconstruction.

1. Mywa

(1)

mywa yi rgyal po kag la boñ zes bya ba // ybañs su pyag ychal nas / (PT 1287: 345)

The king of the Mywa, called Kag-la-boñ, paid homage as a subject.

(2)

dgun bcan pho čhab srid la mywa la gšegs pa las/ dguñ du gšegs/ (ITJ 750: 148)

In the winter, the *bcan po*, upon going on a military campaign against the Mywa, passed away.

(3)

mywa la kag las scogs (266) pa pyag ycald/ (ITJ 750)

The Mywa La-kag, among others, paid homage.

2. White Mywa

(4)

yjañ (335) la čhab srid mjad de mywa dkar po dpyağ phab// mywa nag po ybañsu bkug (PT 1287)

Having enforced [his] policy against the Yjañ, [Khri Xdu-sroñ-brcan] imposed taxes on the White Mywa [and] subjugated the Black Mywa.

(5)

lho pyogs kyī smad na yjañ dum mywa dkar po zes (344) bya ba yi rgyal po sde myī čuñ ba žig ydug (PT 1287)

The king of the branch of the Yjañ called the White Mywa, a small community, was in the lowlands of the southern regions.

(6)

mywa dkar po ybañs su mñay ba las (PT 1287: 393)

[They] took in possession the White Mywa as subjects.

3. Black Mywa

(7)

yjañ (335) la čhab srid mjad de mywa dkar po dpyağ phab// mywa nag po ybañsu bkug (PT 1287)

Having enforced [his] policy against the Yjañ, [Khri Xdu-sroñ-brcan] imposed taxes on the White Mywa [and] subjugated the Black Mywa.

(8)

mywa nag poe po ña la (290) brī pyag ycald/ (ITJ 750)

La-bri, an emissary of the Black Mywa, paid homage.

4. Xjañ-Mywa

(9)

yjañ mywa yi rgyal po lta žig rgya la lta ba las// rgya rjes (348) dgrar blañste// (PT 1287)

The one like a king of Xjañ-Mywa was paying attention to the Chinese. Thereupon, the Chinese lord took him as an enemy.

5. Land of the Mywa

(10)

dgun bcan po khri ydus sroñ mywa yul du čab srid la gšegs gšegs (Dx 12851: v6)

In the winter, *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ was going to the Mywa land for a military campaign.

From (5) we can infer that the White Mywa was a branch of the Xjañ, whereas (4) suggests that the Black Mywa was another branch of the the Xjañ. The compound Xjañ-Mywa confirms the close relationship between the Xjañ and the Mywa but the existence of two different demonyms requires explanation.

In the year preceding (2), the following event is reported:

(11)

dgun bcan po yjañ yul du gšegste/ yjañ phab (ITJ 750: 145)

In the winter, the *bcan po*, having gone to the Xjañ land, defeated the Xjañ people.

For a better overview, we can juxtapose the relevant events from the years 703–5:

(12) 703/4

dgun bcan po yjañ yul du gšegste/ yjañ phab / (ITJ 750: 145)

In the winter, the *bcan po*, having gone to the Xjañ land, defeated the Xjañ people.

(13) 704/5

dgun bcan pho čhab srid la mywa la gšegs pa las/ dguñ du gšegs/ (ITJ 750: 148)

In the winter, the *bcan po*, upon going on a military campaign against the Mywa, passed away.

(14)

dgun bcan po khri ydus sroñ mywa yul du čab srid la gšegs gšegs (Dx 12851: v6)

In the winter, *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ was going to the Mywa land for a military campaign.

There is no reason to assume that *yjañ yul* of 703/4 referred to the same political unit as *mywa yul* just one year later. Thus, at least in the initial phase of their direct contacts, the Tibetans differentiated between the Xjañ and the Mywa. On the other hand, La-kag (r. 728–748) and Kag-la-boñ (r. 748–779) are known from Chinese sources to have been rulers of the united Nanzhao kingdom (Ch. Nánzhào 南詔, lit. ‘Southern Zhao’).²⁶ Their forms of address used in Tibetan sources (*mywa* in (3), *mywa yi rgyal po* in (1)) indicate that around the mid-8th c. Tibetans used the ethnonym *mywa* to refer to the polity known in Chinese sources as Nanzhao. From (12) it occurs that the Xjañ were defeated before the Mywa. In a passage from the OTC (PT 1287: 343–65), which recapitulates the history of the relationship between the Tibetans and the Xjañ~Mywa, Kag-la-boñ is first called *mywa yi rgyal po* but then in the next line he is referred to as *yjañ gi rgyal po*. By comparing the OTC with Chinese sources, we can

²⁶ For their Chinese names, see OTD.

infer that the passage describes an event from the year 751.²⁷ Table 2 gives a chronological overview of the use of *mywa* and *γjañ* in OLT.

I conclude that *γjañ* was a local term borrowed by the Tibetans to first refer to the populations inhabiting roughly the northwestern or western part of the modern Yunnan province. As the Tibetans continued their conquest further south, they made acquaintance with the Mywa people, the main ethnic component of the Nanzhao kingdom, from which also the ruling class came. Since in the first half of the 8th c. the Nanzhao extended their influence, the name Mywa might have become co-extensive with *γjañ*. But the differentiation between *mywa dkar po* and *mywa nag po* indicates that the Tibetans were well aware of the complex ethnic composition of the regional groups. It might be that, despite the prominent position of the Mywa people in the ethnic composition of the Nanzhao kingdom, the term *γjañ* became more popular in Tibetan due to its more familiar, Tibetan-like morphology.

²⁷ (Backus 1981: 71).

Date	OTA	OTC	
Khri Xdus-sroñ-brcan			
703/4	<i>dgun bcan po yjañ yul du gsegste/ yjañ phab</i>	ITJ 750: 145	
704/5	<i>dgun bcan pho čhab srid la mywa la gšegs pa las/ dguñ du gšegs/</i>	ITJ 750: 148	
704/5	<i>dgun bcan po khri ydus sroñ mywa yul du čab srid la gšegs gšegs</i>	Dx 12851: v6	<i>yjañ la čhab srid mjad de mywa dkar po dpyaγ phab// PT 1287: 334–5</i> <i>mywa nag po ybañsu bkug</i> <i>lho pyogs kyī smad na yjañ dum mywa dkar po žes bya ba PT 1287: 343–4</i> <i>yi rgyal po sde myī čuñ ba žig ydug</i>
Khri Lde- gcug-brcan			
733/4	<i>mywa la kag las scogs pa pyag yčald/</i>	ITJ 750: 265–6	
742/3	<i>mywa nag poe po ña la brī pyag yčald/</i>	ITJ 750: 289–90	<i>mywa yī rgyal po kag la boñ žes bya ba // ybañs su pyag PT 1287: 345</i> <i>yčhal nas /</i> <i>yjañ gī rgyal po bod kyī ybañs su bžes pas PT 1287: 346</i> <i>yjañ mywa yī rgyal po lta žig rgya la lta ba las// rgya rjes PT 1287: 347–8</i> <i>dgrar blañste//</i>
Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan			
			<i>mywa dkar po ybañs su mñay ba las PT 1287: 393</i> <i>brag rcer nol thabs bkye ba yi che// yjañ mañ po bkum PT 1287: 394</i> <i>nas//</i> <i>yjañ rje gol gyis kyañ pyag yčhal te/ ybañs rnal mar bkug PT 1287: 396</i> <i>nas/</i>

Table 2. Mywa and Xjañ in OLT sources

📍 **Mywa nag-po** (#780) 'Black Mywa'

📍 **Mywa-yul** (#373) 'Land of the Mywa people'

📍 **Rma-grom** (#269)

Colonial province (*khrom*) on the Upper Yellow River with the centre in Gog-ču (Ch. Kuòzhōu 廓州), re-established by councillor Khri-bzañ and *zañ* Stoñ-rcañ in 755/6 with *zañ* Mdo-bzer as general of the province (Or.8212/187: 13–4). Places related: Yo-ti-ču-bzañs (residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ in S 704/5).

📍 **Rma-bya-cal** (#267)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ's court in W 700/1 (ITJ 750: 134).

📍 **Rma-che** (#268)

City retaken in W 738/9 (ITJ 750: 280).

📍 **Rma-roñ** (#270)

Located in Rag-tag a Mdo-smad council site in W 707/8 and W 759/60 (ITJ 750: 165; Or.8212/187: 37).

C

📍 Cal-ka (#44)

Located in Brag-mar court's residence in W 697/8 (ITJ 750: 126).

📍 Ce-či (#779)

In OLT, Ce-či seems to be a *hapax legomenon*. (Dotson 2009b: 129), following DTH: 63, understood it, apparently, as a toponym. Two arguments speak for its interpretation as a demonym: 1. the following verb phrase *ɣbaŋsu bkug* (Or.8212/187: 22), lit. 'bent as subjects', which in OLT always refers to human beings (see OTDO); and 2. occurrence of similar phrases with demonyms preceding *man čad*:

dbaŋ po man čad ɣbaŋs yoŋs kyis (PT 16: 34r3-4)

luŋ gī rgyal po nuŋ kog man čhad ɣbaŋs su bsdus (PT 1287: 381)

Accordingly, I take Ce-či to be a name of an otherwise unknown people.

📍 Coŋ-ka-čhu-ŋu (#55) 'Little Coŋ-ka'

Region located to the east of Kokonor and captured by councillor Khri-bzaŋ, *žaŋ* Stoŋ-rcan, and *žaŋ* Bcan-ba in W 759/60 (Or.8212/187: 37-8).

📍 Coŋ-ka-čhen-po (#54) 'Great Coŋ-ka'

Stronghold east of the Kokonor lake conquered by great councillor Snaŋ-bžer in W 757/8 (Or.8212/187: 28); identical with Chinese garrison Héyuánjūn 河源军.

📍 Cwa de pu (#582)

Ch. emissary, paid homage in the summer 730/1 (ITJ 750: 256). *Cwa de pu* is a transcription of Ch. family name Cui 崔 and the title *dà-fū* 大夫 (Petech 1988a: 283).

📍 Gcam (#92)

Region including Yul-mar (PT 1288: 31-2).

📍 Gce (#94)

Mdo-smad council site in W 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 48, 78); possibly a larger region, within which Nam-yor (see Gce-nam-yor) was located.

📍 Gce-nam-yor (#93)

Mdo-smad council site in W 709/10, W 710/11, W 711/2, W 720/1, W 722/3, W 723/4, W 726/7, W 757/8, W 758/9, and W 761/2 (ITJ 750: 174, 178, 182, 218, 226, 231, 242;

Or.8212/187: 28, 32, 43, 72–73) where great councillor Xbro Čuñ-bzañ Xor-mañ carried out the administration of Mtoñ-sod in W 730/1 (ITJ 750: 258).

1 **Bcan-to-re Lhas-byin (#22)**

záñ; acted as groomsman of Kim-śañ khoñ čo in 710/11; together with Bcan-zuñ, the king of the Dags-po, prepared the administration of the Xa-ža people at Xo-khol of Sil-gu-čin in S 714/5; died in S 721/2 (ITJ 750: 137–8, 176, 194–5, 207, 210, 212, 216, 217, 220).

1 **Bcan-ba (#21)**

záñ; together with councillor Mgos Khri-bzañ Yab-lag and záñ Stoñ-rcan overthrew Little Coñ-ka in W 759/60; together with Mčhims záñ Rgyal-zigs Śu-theñ, councillor Nan-lam Stag-sgra Klu-khoñ, and záñ Stoñ-rcan overthrew Keñ-śi in 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 37–8, 53–4, 86). His name is transcribed in PC 2555 as *shàng zàn-mó shè-pó-è* 上贊摩射婆萼 (see Fig. 1; (Demiéville 1952: 290, fn. 2); (Horlemann 2002: 61)).²⁸ The transcription of *-ba* with a bilabial nasal *m* may surprise but it could reflect the assimilation of *-b* to the preceding alveolar nasal *-n* in the contemporary local pronunciation: *b- > m- / -n+₋*. The source of the last three syllables of the Chinese transcription is more problematic. If they were indeed part of the name, it must have been his given name. Unfortunately, none of the thus far documented given names resembles the reconstructed values of the Chinese transcription:

	(Schuessler 2007)		(Baxter and Sagart 2014)		(Pulleyblank 1991)		
	LH	OCM	MC	OC	Y.	L.	E.
尚/上 <i>shàng</i>	dʒaŋ ^B	*daŋʔ/djaŋʔ	dzyangX	*Cə-daŋʔ	ʂaŋ`	ʂfiaŋ`	dʒiaŋ ^h
贊 <i>zàn</i>			tsanH	*ts̺arʔ-s	tsan`	tsan`	tsan ^h
摩 <i>mó</i>	mai	*mâi	ma	*m̺aj	mɔ`	mua	ma
射 <i>shè</i>	ʒa ^C	*m-lakh	zyaeH	*Cə.lAk	ʂɛ`	ʂfia`	ʒia ^h
婆 <i>pó</i>	ba (ONW)		ba	*[b̺]a[j]	p ^h ɔ´	phua	ba
萼 <i>è</i>					aw`/ɔ´	ŋak	ŋak

Figure 1. Chinese transcription of Bcan-ba's name

²⁸ I wish to thank Bianca Horlemann for her invaluable help with the identification and transcription of the Chinese characters.

⤴ **Bcan-ma-thog** (#539)

Stemming from the Mčhims family, wife of Khri Ḳdus-sroñ and mother of Khri Lde-gcug-rcan (PT 1286: 65–6); died in W 721/2 (ITJ 750: 223) and was buried in W 723/4 (ITJ 750: 229).

⤴ **Bcan-zuñ** (#58)

The last king of the Dags-po, titled *dbon*; active from ca. 706/7 to 714/5 (ITJ 750: 157, 160, 179–80, 181, 184, 186, 188, 194, 196); prob. the son of Khri-zuñ and *bcan mo* Khri-mo-steñs.

⤴ **Bcan-sroñ** (#398)

According to PT 1288: 8, Bcan-sroñ was a younger brother of *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan with whom he was also fighting. The passage is damaged and so nothing about the fate of Bcan-sroñ is known apart from the fact that Khri Sroñ-rcan apparently won and retained the power. Since the fight is mentioned right after the successful military campaign against the Ḳa-ža and Chinese (PT 1288: 6–7), in which *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan seems to have personally participated, we can speculate that in his absence Bcan-sroñ attempted to usurp the throne. Bcan-sroñ is not mentioned in any other OLT text.

📍 **Rcañ** (#275)

Region encompassing Śañs and Ḳo-yug valleys. Related places: Gliñ-kar-chal (council site of W 690/1).

📍 **Rcañ-čhen** (#476) ‘Great Rcañ’

Great Rcañ bordered to the east on Rcañ and was included into the Four Horns after 733/4 as Upper Rcañ. Great Rcañ had had four *mñans*, reduced to two in 684/5 (ITJ 750: 89). It also had a *bruñ pa* official; its *bruñ pa* Lañ Sa-ceñ died in 715/6 and was replaced by *žañ* Khri-mñes Smon-zuñ (ITJ 750: 199), whereas *bruñ pa* Ža-sña Thañ-rcan was dismissed and replaced by Señ-go Mon-bu in 731/2 (ITJ 750: 260–1).

⤴ **Rcañ-rhyay** (#249)

A people, probably neighbouring the Glo-bo, subjugated by grand councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ in 652/3.

📍 **Rcibs** (#477)

Located in Že-siñ residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 715/6 (ITJ 750: 198).

ch

📍 **Cha-steñs** (#46)

Located in Xo-yug place where grand councillor Mgar Khri-γbriñ Bcan-brod made an account of border guards in S 690/1 (ITJ 750: 104).

📍 **Chañ-bañ-sna** (#47)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in W 674/5 (ITJ 750: 60) where he died in W 676/7 (ITJ 750: 66–7); council site of W 719/20 (ITJ 750: 212).

📍 **Chur-luñ** (#52)

Located in Žogs council site of W 688/9 (ITJ 750: 101).

📍 **Ches-poñ Tre-goñ** (#525)

Installed as *bruñ pa* in S 714/5 (ITJ 750: 194) and removed from the post in W 745/6 (ITJ 750: 301). Between 714/5 and 745/6 he acquired the title *žañ*. This is possibly related to the fact that in 742/3 *bcan po* Sroñ-lde-brcan (alias Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan) was born (ITJ 750: 291–2). According to PT 1286: 67–8, Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan's wife was Rma-rgyal Ldoñ-skar from the Ches-poñ family. This would, however, mean that the main wife was determined soon after the heir to the throne was born. If this interpretation is correct this would mean that by that time *žañ* was already used as a title detached from its original meaning 'maternal uncle'.

📍 **Mchar-bu-sna** (#401)

Located in Sre-ga the residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 725/6 and 731/2 (ITJ 750: 236, 259); residence of *bcan po*'s court in S 726/7, S729/30, and S 742/3 (ITJ 750: 239, 252, 289). Places related: Ñañ-mo-gliñ (residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 740/1).

📍 **Mcho-bgo** (#194)

Region including Bol-gañs (residence of Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 728/9).

📍 **Mcho-nag-stoñ-ru** (#195)

Place of a battle between Mañ-po-rje, king of the Dags-po, and the Chinese general Seyu *den pañ* in 659/60 (PT 1288: 37).

J

📍 **Brjen-tań** (#35)

Located in Mal-tro residence of the *bcan po* in 694/5, S 713/4 and S 714/5, and council site in S 761/2 and S 761/2 (ITJ 750: 116, 188, 193; Or.8212/187: 42, 70).

W

Ž

⤴ **Ža-sña Thań-rcan** (#335)

bruñ pa of Great Rcañ dismissed in W 731/2 (ITJ 750: 261).

📍 **Žań-cal** (#730)

Located in Žo-don place where administration of a colonial province was carried out in S 741/2 (ITJ 750: 285).

⤴ **Žań-žuń** (#384)

A people inhabiting the region of Gu-ge, Ma-pañ (Manasarovar), Ti-se (Kailash), Dar-ma and Byañ valleys. In OLT records names of their two rulers are preserved: Lig Myi-rhya (married to Sad-mar-kar; PT 1287: 398–9) and prob. his son Lig Sña-śur. They were ultimately conquered by Khri Sroń-rcan in 644/5. In 653/4 Spug-gyim Rcan-rma-čhuń was appointed as *mñan* of the Žań-žuń land (*žañ žuń yul*). Their administration was carried out by grand councillor Mgar Stoń-rcan Yul-zuń at Du-gul in 662/3, by councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu at Gu-rand of Žims in S 675/6, and together with the Mard people during a council at Chań-bañ-sna in W 719/20. They revolted in 677/8 after the death of Khri Mań-slon Mań-rcan but the revolt was suppressed.

📍 **Žań-žuń-yul** (#385) ‘Žań-žuń land’

📍 **Žims** (#338)

Region including Gu-rand.

📍 **Žur** (#348)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan (*alias* Rgyal-gcug-ru) and Khri-ma-lod in W 705/6 (ITJ 750: 153).

📍 **Že-šiń** (#478)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Mań-slon Mań-rcan in the spring 675/6 (ITJ 750: 62). Places related: Rcibs (residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 715/6).

📍 **Žo-thañ** (#341)

Located in Ñas Mdo-smad council site of S 761/2 (Or.8212/187: 42, 71).

📍 **Žo-don** (#729)

Ch. town to the west of modern Xining 西寧. Places related: Žań-cal.

📍 **Žogs** (#343)

Region including Chur-luñ (council site of W 688/9); valley entrance: N 29°49'55.88, E 91°28'5.83.

📍 **Žon-ba** (#508)

Located in Zu-spug council site in S 694/5 (ITJ 750: 116).

📍 **Gžon-phyag** (#111)

Council site in S 711/2 (ITJ 750: 179).

Z

📍 **Zaṅs-kar** (#336)

Conquered by *žaṅ* Stoṅ-rcaṅ together with Zoṅ-ču in W 761/2 (Or.8212/187: 45, 74).

📍 **Zar-phu** (#337)

Located in Dra council site of S 719/20 (ITJ 750: 210). Identical with LT Gzar-poṅi phu (Ch. Sàpǔ 萨普; N 29°0'39, E 91°18'21) of Upper Grwa.

📍 **Zin-ču** (#339)

Ch. stronghold captured together with Ḳbu-śiṅ-kun and Ga-ču by *žaṅ* Rgyal-zigs and *žaṅ* Stoṅ-rcaṅ in 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 52, 84).

📍 **Zu-spug** (#506)

Council site in S 688/9 and residence of *bcan po* Khri Sroṅ-lde-brcaṅ's court in S 758/9 (ITJ 750: 100; Or.8212/187: 29–30); identified with modern Zi/Gzi-sbug (Ch. Sībù 斯布) of eastern Mal-gro (= OLT Mal-tro; valley entrance: N 29°43'30.39, E 91°53'40.08). Places related: Żon-ba (council site in S 694/5), Rkyaṅ-bu-chal (council site in S 713/4 and 715/6), and Sdiṅs (residence of *bcan po* Khri Sroṅ-lde-brcaṅ's court in S 761/2).

📍 **Zuṅ-kar** (#347)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Sroṅ-lde-brcaṅ in S 756/7 and W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 17, 19).

📍 **Zoṅ-ču** (#342)

Chinese stronghold conquered by *žaṅ* Stoṅ-rcaṅ in W 761/2 (Or.8212/187: 45, 74).

📍 **Zol** (#344)

Located in Mdo-smad council site of 732/3 and 733/4 (ITJ 750: 264, 267).

📍 **Zrid** (#346)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Maṅ-slon Maṅ-rcaṅ in S 674/5 (ITJ 750: 60) identical with modern valley Sbra-kha-dam-pa (valley entrance: N 30°21'19.79, E 91°3'47.93). The name is preserved in modern Ḳbri-smad and Ḳbri-ču-kha. Places related: Ldu-nag (residence of *bcan po* Khri Maṅ-slon Maṅ-rcaṅ in 665/6 and 669/70; council site in S 728/9) and Ldu-nag-slad-ma (residence of *bcan po* Khri Maṅ-slon Maṅ-rcaṅ in 666/7).

📍 **Zrid-mday** (#345)

Council site in S 681/2 and residence of *bcan po* Khri Ṭdus-sroñ in 696/7 (ITJ 750: 78, 123), identical with modern Ṭbri-smad.

Bacot observed that a monastery of Sri-mday is mentioned in *Bstan ṷgyur* (DTH: 32, fn. 9). Indeed, in the colophon to Śāntideva's *Śikṣāsamuccaya* (CT *Bslab pa kun las btus pa*) we read:

(1)

slad kyi kha čheyi pañḍi ta ti la ka ka la śa dañ / lo cā ba dge sloñ blo ldan śes rab kyi sri mdayi dgon par źu tug (read: *dag*) *legs par byas payo /* (D 3940, *dbu ma*, *khi* 194v5; *apud* BCRD)

Ti-la-ka-ka-la-śa, a *pañḍita* from farther Kashmir, and *lo cā ba* monk Blo-lDan Śes-rab prepared well the correction at the monastery of Sri-mday.

According to BDRC, *sri mday* recurs in KhG in the phrase *sri mdayi brag tu* 'at the rocks of Sri-mday' which, however, I was not able to trace in the text. Since modern reflexes of OLT *zr-* differ from those of *sr-*, it seems very unlikely that OLT *Zrid-mday* should be equated with this *Sri-mday*. Even more so since no monastery is known to have existed in the vicinity of the place identified by Hazod (2014: 55, fn. 28) as erstwhile *Zrid-mday* (p.c. 07.10.2017).²⁹

📍 **Zlo** (#340)

Council site in Sp 726/7 and W 734/5 (ITJ 750: 241, 269).

📍 **Gzen** (#110)

Unidentified place located in Mñald (PT 1288: 9).

📍 **Bzañ-sum-chal** (#43)

Council site in W 687/8, W 693/4, and W 720/1 (ITJ 750: 99, 115, 217).

📍 **Bzo-źal-čos** (#451)

Dotson interpreted it as a toponym (Dotson 2009b: 122, fn. 309). I follow the reading of Bacot (DTH: 51). Although the name has an unusual form, the detailed analysis of the verb involved (see LS, s.v. *brgal*) has confirmed that *Bzo-źal-čos* must have been a personal name. *Bzo-źal-čos* seems to have partaken in the military campaign against Chinese reported in 741/2. He is said to have regained for the Tibetans the stronghold *Lčags-rce*.

²⁹ Guntram Hazod also kindly informed me that *Sri* in *Sri-mday* should be identified with a valley of the same name in the vicinity of *Chal-guñ-thañ*, east of *Lha-sa*. *Sri*, today usually spelled *Dkri* or *Kri*, is known as the place where the so-called *Žol-rdo-riñs* (also known as *Sri-rdo-riñ*) originally stood (p.c., 07.10.2017).

Y

📍 **Ya-ga-cal** (#112)

Located in *Yon* residence of *bcan po* Khri *Ydus-sroñ* in W 690/1 and W 697/8 (ITJ 750: 105, 126).

👤 **Ya-ža** (#364)

A Mongolic-speaking people³⁰ identical with Tǔyùhún 吐谷渾 of Ch. sources and inhabiting the region to the west and south of the Kokonor lake in modern Qinghai. They were first attacked by the Tibetans around 637/8 and finally defeated in 663. Their ruler received *bcan mo* Khri-baṅs as bride in 689/90 (ITJ 750: 102). The Ya-ža's administration was carried out by grand councillor Mgar Khri-ybriñ Bcan-brod in 696/7, by Bcan-zuñ (the king of the Dags-po) and *žañ* Bcan-to-re Lhas-byin in S 714/5, and by councillor Čog-ro Mañ-po-rje Khyi-čuñ in S 742/3. Their census was made in S 734/5.

📍 **Ya-ža-yul** (#363) 'Ya-ža land'

Conquered between 659/60 and 665/6 by grand councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ. Its administration was carried out by grand councillor Mgar Khri-ybriñ Bcan-brod in W 693/4 and by Bcan-zuñ (the king of the Dags-po) and *žañ* Bcan-to-re Lhas-byin in S 714/5. Places related: Sil-gu-čin and therin *Yo-khol*.

📍 **Yo-khol** (#125)

Located in Sil-gu-čin of the Ya-ža land place where administration of the Ya-ža was carried out in 696/7 by great councillor Mgar Khri-ybriñ Bcan-brod and in S 714/5 by Bcan-zuñ (the king of the Dags-po) and *žañ* Bcan-to-re Lhas-byin (ITJ 750: 123, 195).

📍 **Yo-dañ** (#124)

Located in Yar-ybrog residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in 670/1 and of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 745/6 (PT 1288: 51; ITJ 750: 147, 300; Or.8212/187: 4; Dx 12851v: 5).

📍 **Yo-bar-chal** (#123)

Council site in W 696/7 (ITJ 750: 124).

³⁰ Para-Mongolic according to (Vovin 2015).

📍 **Y_o-yug** (#126)

Region of *rkañ*-conscriptio in S 735/6 (ITJ 750: 271–2). Places related: Nubs (council site of W 715/6) and Cha-steñs (border guards' counting in S 690/1); valley entrance: N 29°21'41.74, E 89°38'19.26.

📍 **Y_on** (#130)

Region including Sna-bo (residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in W 675/6) and Ya-ga-cal (residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ in W 690/1 and W 697/8); valley entrance: N 29°18'30.69, E 91°49'40.45.

📍 **Y_on-cañ-do** (#129)

Residence of Khri-ma-lod in W 700/1 and W 702/3, and council site in W 702/3, W 707/8, W 708/9, and W 709/10 (ITJ 750: 134, 141, 142, 164, 168, 173). Modern name: Xu-śañ, on the left bank of the Skyi-čhu river about twenty miles downstream from Lhasa (Tucci 1950: 15); (Richardson 1953: 9). *-do* could be an assimilated form of **mdo* 'confluence': m- > Ø / C_C.

📍 **Y_om-bu-cal** (#128)

Located in Brag-mar residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in W 731/2 and court's residence in W 732/3, W 733/4, W 734/5, and W 735/6 (ITJ 750: 260, 263, 266, 269, 272).

📍 **Y_or-mañ** (#131)

bcan po Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan's sojourn in 667/8 (PT 1288: 48).

📍 **Y_ol-byag** (#127)

Located in Gliñ residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ in S 703/4 (ITJ 750: 143), perhaps identical with modern Yos-čhags (Ch. Yóuqiàxiāng 油恰乡; N 30°35'38.36", E 91°52'47.06").

👤 **Y_wañ ydo sí** (#132)

Ch. emissary who paid homage in S 734/5 and W 737/8 (ITJ 750: 268, 277–8).

👤 **Y_wañ zañ só** (#574)

Ch. general (*dmag pon*) against whom Mgar Khri-ybriñ Bcan-brod won a battle at Stag-la-rgya-dur (in the Ya-ža land) in W 695/6 (ITJ 750: 122). The name could be a transcription of Ch. family name Wáng³¹ 王 and the title *shàng-shū* 尚書.³² The same person is introduced as a

³¹ Petech reconstructed *ywañ* in *Ywañ ydo sí* (see s.v.) as a transcription of Ch. Wáng 王 (Petech 1988a: 285).

Chinese councillor (*blon po*) and general (*dmag pon*) in PT 1287: 495–6, although his name is spelled as either $\text{Xwoñ-ker } \check{Z}\text{añ-še}$ (PT 1287: 495, 496, 497) or $\text{Xweñ-ker } \check{Z}\text{añ-še}$ (PT 1287: 512, 521). In the OTC, an entire chapter is devoted to the battle between Mgar Khri-γbriñ Bcan-brod and $\text{Xwañ } \check{z}\text{añ } \acute{s}\text{o}$ at Stag-la-rgya-dur (PT 1287: 495–525).

³² Petech reconstructed *zān só* in *Jeyu zān só* (see s.v.) as a transcription of Ch. *shàng-shū* 尚書 (Petech 1988a: 280).

Y

1 Yañ kheñ (#575)

Ch. emissary, paid homage in the summer 713/4 (ITJ 750: 190). Yañ *kheñ* is a transcription of Ch. family name Yáng 楊 and the title *qīng* 卿 (Petech 1988a: 282).

1 Yam-ču (#330)

A petitioner from Kwa-ču (Or.8212/187: 87).

9 Yar-ybrog (#331)

Region including Xjon (residence of Khri-ma-lod in S 702/3) and Xo-dañ (residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in 670/1, of Khri-ma-lod in S 704/5, and of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 745/6).

1 Yu-sna-kug-ti (#543)

A Nepalese (OLT Bal-po) king Jiṣṇagupta or Viṣṇugupta who usurped the throne in 631 and was killed by Tibetans in 642/3 (PT 1288: 12; (Bialek 2018c: 23)).

9 Yul-mar (#334)

Located in Gcam place of a hunt organised by grand councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ in 656/7 (PT 1288: 31–2).

9 Yo-ti-ču-bzañs (#332)

Located in Rma-grom residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ in S 704/5 (ITJ 750: 146–7).

9 Yol (#333)

Located in Mdo-smad region and council site of W 718/9, W 719/20, S 756/7, and W 756/7 (ITJ 750: 209, 214; Or.8212/187: 22, 23). Places related: Či-ybos (council site of W 703/4) and Rteyu-dkyus (council site of 706/7).

9 G.yag-ru-goñ (#84)

Located in Ba-bams residence of the court in S 757/8 (Or.8212/187: 24).

9 G.yag-ru-thañ (#85)

Located in Ba-bams council site in W 680/1 (ITJ 750: 77).

📍 **G.yug** (#88)

Located in Rkoñ place where grand councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcañ Yul-zuñ organised a yak-hunt in 653/4 (PT 1288: 23–4) and *bcañ po* Khri Mañ-slon-mañ-rcañ went for hunting in 662/3 (PT 1288: 41).

📍 **G.ye-thal-ba-goñ** (#86)

Located in Sñiñ-druñ place of residence of grand councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcañ Yul-zuñ in S 657/8 (PT 1288: 33).

📍 **G.yo-ru** (#87) 'Left Horn; administrative unit'

r

📍 **Ra-sñon** (#246)

Located in Ltam residence of *bcan po* Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in S 671/2 (PT 1288: 52).

📍 **Ra-mchar** (#244)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 743/4 and S 744/5 (ITJ 750: 293, 296).

📍 **Ra-sa** (#245)

Later renamed as Lha-sa; included Śa-cal (ITJ 750: 177).

📍 **Rag-tag** (#248)

A region in Mdo-smad; places related: Rma-roñ (council site in W 707/8, W 759/60), Ñam-pu (council site in W 708/9), and Kog (council site in W 755/6).

Identified with Ch. Luòtuó 駱駝 (Petech 1988a: 273) but the second syllable has been reconstructed as open Y. t^hɔ'/L. tʰa/E. da (Pulleyblank 1991: 314).³³

📍 **Rab-ka-cal** (#247)

Located in Śaṅs court residence in W 673/4 and council site of W 684/5 (ITJ 750: 58, 88); possibly located in Ra-kha valley (valley entrance: N 29°37'40.02, E 89°1'14.26).

👤 **Riñ-cug Skor-dañ** (#263)

Recorded because of his disloyalty in connection with a revolt of the Žaṅ-žuṅ people in 677/8 (ITJ 750: 69–70).

👤 **Rid-stag-rhya** (#262)

Councillor of the lord of the Ra-saṅ; arranged great exchange of fields in 653/4 (PT 1288: 24).

📍 **Ris-pu** (#264)

Place where great councillor Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuṅ died in 667/8 (PT 1288: 48); modern Ri-phu (Ch. Ribù 日布; N 30°16'12.00, E 91°8'14.00).

📍 **Ru-bží** (#378) 'Four-Horns'

Administrative system introduced in 732/3 or 733/4 that integrated the Three Horns (OLT *ru gsum*), the Dependent Horn (OLT *ru lag*), and the Great Rcañ (OLT *rcañ čhen*).

³³ No reconstruction in (Baxter and Sagart 2014) and (Schuessler 2007).

📍 **Ru-yoñ Phyi-gseñ (#568)**

A *bruñ pa*, died in 719/20 (ITJ 750: 211).

📍 **Ru-riñs (#276)**

Council site in 680/1 (ITJ 750: 75).

📍 **Ru-lag (#367)** ‘Dependent Horn’

An administrative unit distinct from the Three Horns (OLT *ru gsum*) and the Great Rcañ (OLT *rcañ čhen*), but integrated into the Four Horns in 732/3 or 733/4.

📍 **Ru-gsum (#370)** ‘Three Horns’

Administrative system that consisted of the Left Horn (OLT *g.yo ru*), the Right Horn, and the Central Horn and was replaced by the Four Horns (OLT *ru bži*) in 732/3 or 733/4.

📍 **Re-kras-yjoñ (#251)**

Mdo-smad council site in S 757/8 (Or.8212/187: 26).

📍 **Re-skam (#253)**

Located in Dbu-ru-śod council site in 684/5 (ITJ 750: 86–7); modern Rol-skam, Ch. Ruògòng 若贡, in Lhun-grub county (N 30° 3'57.77, E 91°40'15.18).

📍 **Re-luñ-bzañs (#252)**

Mdo-smad council site in S 760/1 (Or.8212/187: 41, 69); also mentioned in a damaged passage in PT 1285: v148.

📍 **Reyu-cal (#254)**

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Ṭdus-sroñ in W 694/5 (ITJ 750: 117).

📍 **Ryam-śi-gar (#277)**

Mdo-smad council site in W 692/3, W 717/8, and W 721/2 (ITJ 750: 113, 206, 222).

📍 **Ryu-bye (#279)**

Located in Glag council site in early winter 678/9 (ITJ 750: 72).

1 Rye-sin Khu-bul-bu (#278)

Recorded because of his disloyalty in connection with a revolt of the Žañ-zuñ people in 677/8 (ITJ 750: 69). The family name recurs in Rye-sin Pya-ligstañ, a name of a donor inscribed on a rock in eastern Wakhan corridor (Mock 2018: 6ff.)

I

1 La-kag (#158)

Official of the Mywa, paid homage in 733/4 (ITJ 750: 265). Identified with the Nangzhao ruler known in Chinese sources as Pí Luógé 皮羅閣 (Stein 1952: 83).

1 La-bri (#157)

Emissary of the Black Mywa; paid homage in S 742/3 (ITJ 750: 289–90).

9 La-mo-čhag-pa-prum (#163)

Residence of Dbays Phańs-to-re Dbyi-chab (PT 1287: 248–61) identified with La-mo-čhag-deyu (Ch. Lā Mùqūguǒ 拉木曲果; N 29°47'22.18, E 91°33'38.36) in La-mo, a side valley of Skyi-čhu.

1 Lañ-gro Khoñ-rcan (#159)

Installed as a councillor of Kim-šeñ khoñ čo in W 730/1 (ITJ 750: 257, 290).

1 Lañ-gro Sña-brcan Khoñ-lod (#160)

mñan dismissed in S 723/4 (ITJ 750: 227–8).

1 Lañ Xbal (#161)

The families Lañ and Xbal, whose serfs were banished to Mtoñ-sod in 755/6 and their wealth appraised and confiscated in W 755/6 and S 756/7.

1 Lañ Myes-zigs (#162)

Grand councillor together with Xbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-chab accused of disloyalty, killing of *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan, and threatening his successor *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan (Or.8212/187: 8; Żol S 5–17).

1 Lañ Sa-ceñ (#526)

bruñ pa of the Great Rcañ; died in 715/6 (ITJ 750: 199).

1 Li *kheñ* (#583)

Ch. emissary, paid homage in the summer 732/3 (ITJ 750: 262–3). Li *kheñ* is a transcription of Ch. family name Lǐ 李 and the title *qīng* 卿 (Petech 1988a: 284).

♣ **Li coñ kan** (#570)

Ch. emissary who paid homage in the winter 729/30 (ITJ 750: 253–4). *Li coñ kan* is a transcription of the Chinese family name 李 *Lǐ* and the title 總管 *zǒng-guǎn* (Petech 1988a: 282).

♣ **Li źaň só** (#584)

Ch. emissary, paid homage in 733/4 (ITJ 750: 265–6) and in the winter 736/7 (ITJ 750: 274). *Li źaň só* is a transcription of Ch. family name 李 *Lǐ* and the title *shàng-shū* 尚書 (Petech 1988a: 285).

♣ **Lig Sña-śur** (#)

Ruler of the *Žaň-žuň* people called 'lord of Dar-ma' (*dar maḡi rje bo*; PT 1286: 7; PT 1290: r3, v5) and conquered in 644/5 (PT 1288: 13–4); prob. the son of Lig Myi-rhya.

♣ **Luň-riňs** (#185)

Located in Rgyas council site in 681/2 (ITJ 750: 80).

♣ **Leň-ču** (#413)

Located within the colonial province of Khar-can (Or.8212/187: 33), corresponds to Ch. Liángzhōu 涼州區.

Ś

📍 Śa-gu-ñiñ-sum-khol (#282)

Destination of a military campaign in S 700/1 (ITJ 750: 132).

📍 Śa-cal (#281)

Place in Ra-sa where *bcan mo* Kim-śaṅ khoṅ čo was received in 710/11 (ITJ 750: 177).

📍 Śa-ra (#283)

Located in Sprags residence of Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in 659/60, 668/9 and S 676/7 (PT 1288: 36, 49; ITJ 750: 66).

📍 Śa-ru-mkhar (#284)

Located in Bal-po residence of Khri Lde-gcug-rcan in S 708/9 (ITJ 750: 166).

📍 Śaṅs (#285)

Region including Rab-ka-cal (court's sojourn in W 673/4 and council site of W 684/5), Sum-ču-bo (Mañ-slon-mañ-rcan's residence in S 672/3 and S 673/4), and possibly Nam-ce-gliñ (Khri Mañ-slon-mañ-rcan's sojourn in W 672/3); valley entrance: N 29°24'57.77, E 89°4'48.81.

📍 Śig-nig (#380)

A people from the Upper Regions whose emissaries paid homage together with the Black Ban-ŷjag and the Gog in W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 20). The partially preserved manuscript Or.15000/400, mentions Sig-nis in the following context:

(1)

stod na/ sig nis la čhab srid mjad pa[ŷ]i [-] (Or.15000/400: r4)

In the upper [part], [one who] ruled over the Sig-nis.³⁴

Its location in the upper part (*stod*) supports Takeuchi's suggestion that Sig-nis could be the same place as Śig-nig of the OTA (Takeuchi 1998: 167, Text 516).

📍 Śud-pu Khoṅ-zuṅ (#324)

Replaced in S 742/3 (ITJ 750: 290).

³⁴ For *čhab srid mjad*, see (Bialek 2022c: 32).

📍 **Śo-ma-ra** (#312)

Located in Skyi council site in W 729/30, W 731/2, and W 744/5 (ITJ 750: 254, 260, 298; Or.8212/187: 3).

📍 **Śoñ-sna** (#313)

Council site in S 686/7 and S 692/3 (ITJ 750: 95, 111).

S

📍 Sa-byar (#280)

Residence of the court in S 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 45, 75).

📍 Sin-čaŋ (#727)

Ch. stronghold located in Kwa-ču and sacked by Tibetans in S 727/8 (ITJ 750: 244).

📍 Sil-gu-čin (#299)

Region located in the Xa-ža land; related place: Xo-khol.

📍 Sum-ču-bo (#325)

Located in Śaŋs residence of Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan in S 672/3 and S 673/4, and place of grand councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu's death in 685/6 (ITJ 750: 54, 56, 91).

👤 Sum-pa (#326)

A people inhabiting the region to the northeast of the Four Horns (*ru bži*) administered as Sum-ru (Sum-pa Horn); prob. identical with Sūnbō 孫波 of Ch. sources. They were conquered at the end of the 6th c. during the reign of Khri Slon-mchan. Their dice code was adopted by the council of Mdo-smad at Rgyam-śi-gar in W 692/3.

📍 Sum-ru (#382)

Administrative unit whose administration was carried out during the Mdo-smad council at Nam-ldoŋ-prom in W 702/3 (ITJ 750: 141).

📍 Se-ču (#288)

Ch. Suízhōu 肅州 captured by councillor Mgos Khri-bzaŋ Yab-lag, žaŋ Stoŋ-rcan, and Kag-la-boŋ in W 756/7 (Or.8212/187: 22). (Horlemann 2002: 60, fn. 28) identified Se-ču with Xīzhōu 西州 = Turfan.

👤 Se-rib (#)

A people nowadays inhabiting the upper Kali Gandaki valley (Thak Khola) south of the Glo-bo (Mustang, Nepal). They revolted in W 705/6 and their king was seized in W 709/10.

📍 Seg-śiŋ-kun (#295)

Ch. stronghold captured together with the Great Coŋ-ka (*coŋ ka čhen po*) by great councillor Snaŋ-bžer in W 757/8 (Or.8212/187: 29).

♣ **Señ-go Snañ-to-re Skyi-zuñ (#294)**

Active in Sp 701/2 (ITJ 750: 138).

♣ **Señ-go Xphan-la-skyes (#292)**

Official dismissed in W 745/6 (ITJ 750: 301).

♣ **Señ-go Xbriñ-rcan Mon-čuñ (#291)**

mñan; dismissed in S 723/4 and banished to Chañ-bañ-sna in W 725/6 (ITJ 750: 228, 237).

♣ **Señ-go Mon-bu (#293)**

Appointed as *bruñ pa* in S 719/20 and as *bruñ pa* of the Great Rcañ in W 731/2 (ITJ 750: 211, 261).

♦ **Seb (#290)**

Located in Mdo-smad council site of 734/5 (ITJ 750: 270).

♣ **Seyu Den-pañ (#296)**

Ch. general who fought with Mañ-po-rje, the king of the Dags-po, at Mcho-nag-stoñ-ru in 659/60 (PT 1288: 37).

♦ **So-ga-soñ (#311)**

Ch. stronghold conquered in W 720/1 (ITJ 750: 218).

♣ **Sog-dag (#731)**

Sogdians; name borrowed from Sgd. *swγdyk*; cf. Skt. *sogdaka*.

♦ **Sre-ga (#402)**

Region including Mc(h)ar-bu-sna (ITJ 750: 239, 252).

♦ **Sreyu-gźug (#318)**

Council site in S 691/2 (ITJ 750: 108), possibly including Khra-sna and Lha-gśegs.

♦ **Sla-śod (#303)**

Region located in Mdo-smad and including Snig.

📍 **Slo** (#304)

Council site in W 759/60 (Or.8212/187: 36).

📍 **Gser-khuñ** (#107)

Hunting place of Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ in S 746/7 (Or.8212/187: 7).

📍 **Gser-za** (#108)

Residence of *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ in S 701/2 (ITJ 750: 135).

h

📍 Lha-gab (#172)

Council site of S 707/8, S 712/3, and 726/7 (ITJ 750: 160, 185, 239); related place: Bye-ma-luñ.

📍 Lha-sgal (#176)

Residence of *bcan po*'s court (Or.8212/187: 92).

👤 Lha-spañs (#179)

Sister (*lčam*) of Khri Lde-gcug-rcan; passed away in S 730/1 and was buried in W 732/3 (ITJ 750: 256, 264).

👤 Lha-bal-pho (#171)

(Kapstein 2000: 217, fn. 41): *Ldeyu Jo-sras*, pp. 120–121, states that Khri Lde-gcug-bcan had an elder brother Pa-chab-cha Lha Bal-po, a younger brother Lod Ma-lod, and a son Ljañ-cha Lha-dbon, who died before his Chinese bride arrived in Tibet.

Prob. elder brother of Khri Ḫdus-sroñ, born to Khri Mañ-slön Mañ-rcan and Mañ-pañs, and overthrown from the throne at Poñ-lag-rañ in 705/6 (ITJ 750: 152).

📍 Lha-ri-mo (#175)

Located in Dbu-le a Mdo-smad council site of S 762/4 (Or.8212/187: 47, 77).

📍 Lha-luñ (#174)

Located in Sgrebs birth place of Khri Ḫdus-sroñ in W 676/7 (ITJ 750: 67).

📍 Lha-gśeḡs (#173)

Place located in Sreyu-gźug (?; ITJ 750: 109).

📍 Lhas-gañ-chal (#178)

Located in Lhas valley (modern Gru-bźi; valley entrance: N 29°44'9.98, E 91°27'12.31) residence of Khri-ma-lod in W 704/5, W 707/8, W 708/9, W 709/10, W 710/11, W 711/2, and council site in W 724/5, W 727/8, W 732/3, and W 733/4 (ITJ 750: 148–149, 163, 168, 172, 178, 181, 235, 246, 263, 266).

👤 Lhas-bon (#177)

Son of Khri Lde-gcug-rcan and *jo mo* Khri-bcun; died young in Dron in S 739/40 and was buried in W 741/2 (ITJ 750: 281, 287).

👤 **Lho (#784)**

Family name.

👤 **Lho ᠶᠳᠤᠰ-ᠰᠢᠷᠭᠢᠰ (#181)**

Accused in S 706/7 (ITJ 750: 157).

👤 **Lho ᠶᠪᠷᠢᠨ-ᠫᠣ-ᠷᠭᠢᠶ᠋ᠠᠰᠤᠰᠢᠷᠭᠢᠰ (#180)**

bruᠨ pa (ITJ 750: 83).

q

1 **Qañ ydo sí** (#376)

Ch. emissary who paid homage in S 762-4 (Or.8212/187: 46).

1 **Qan da lañ** (#571)

Ch. emissary who paid homage in S 742/3 (ITJ 750: 289). *Qan da lañ* is a transcription of Ch. family name 安 Ān and the title 大郎 *dà-láng* (Petech 1988a: 287).

Corpus

PT 1288	<i>Old Tibetan Annals</i>
ITJ 750	<i>Old Tibetan Annals</i>
Or.8212/187	<i>Old Tibetan Annals</i>

Symbols and Abbreviations

📍	toponym
👤	anthroponym
[...]	passage left out
#123	lemma's number in the database on OTDO
ABS	absolute
ALL	allative
Ch.	Chinese
CT	Classical Tibetan
D	dental plosive
Dx	Russian: Дх < Дуньхуан
E	east-facing inscription
E.	Early Middle Chinese
ERG	ergative
fig.	figurative(ly)
ITJ	IOL Tib J
KC	Kuki-Chin
Kh.	Khotanese
Lčaŋ	Lčaŋ-bu inscription
L	liquid consonant
L.	Late Middle Chinese
LT	Literary Tibetan
met.	metaphoric(ally)
N	north-facing inscription
OLT	Old Literary Tibetan
Or.	Oriental Collections of the British Library
orig.	original(ly)
OTA	<i>Old Tibetan Annals</i>
OTC	<i>Old Tibetan Chronicles</i>
OTurk.	Old Turkic
PC	Pelliot chinois
PT	¹ Proto-Tibetic; ² Pelliot tibétain
PY	Pinyin
Rkoŋ	Rkoŋ-po inscription
Q	oblique
S	¹ subject; ² summer; ³ south-facing inscription
Skar	Skar-čuŋ inscription
Skt.	Sanskrit
Sp	spring
Turk.	Turkic
W	winter
Y.	Early Mandarin
Žol	Žol inscription
Žwa	Žwayi lha-khaŋ inscription

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